
Queuing Management in Practice

Employing and Applying Queuing Management in Humanitarian Registration and Assistance Delivery Activities

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Preface and Acknowledgments

This dissertation is submitted in partial fulfilment of the requirements for the Master of Science in Data Science at the University of Essex. The research presented in this document discusses the intersection between Queuing Management and Humanitarian Applications, which inspired the title of this dissertation: “**Queuing Management in Practice: Employing and Applying Queuing Management in Humanitarian Registration and Assistance Delivery Activities**”. It explores the application of queuing theory in humanitarian contexts, specifically its role in optimising registration and assistance delivery activities through computational simulations.

The motivation for this research stems from the growing challenges humanitarian organisations face in managing large-scale aid distribution efficiently. With nearly 123 million displaced individuals, according to the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR) (UNHCR, 2024b), relying on these services, reducing wait times and improving resource allocation can significantly impact the well-being of vulnerable populations.

This study aims to adopt a computational modelling approach, integrating queuing theory and management principles into a simulation-based artefact that provides actionable insights for humanitarian organisations. By bridging the gap between theoretical queuing models and real-world crisis management, this research aims to contribute to data science and humanitarian logistics.

Apart from the semantics and formalities, as you read through this dissertation, I hope you find not only a rigorous academic analysis but also a testament to the potential of data science in making a tangible difference in people’s lives. I sincerely hope this research contributes, even if in a small way, to improving the efficiency and effectiveness of humanitarian aid delivery.

This research journey has been both challenging and rewarding, involving an extensive literature review, methodological refinements, and iterative simulation testing, which was made even more demanding by my prior unfamiliarity with this topic. The work reflects not only my academic growth but also my commitment to using technology for social

good.

As such, first and foremost, I would like to express my deepest gratitude to my academic supervisors, Dr Bakhtiyar Ahmed and Dr Samuel Danso, for the invaluable guidance, insightful feedback, and unwavering support throughout this research, going above and beyond to make sure that I achieve this academic milestone. This dissertation would not have been possible without your steadfast guidance, encouragement, and frequent check-ins.

I am also grateful to the University of Essex and especially the Computing Support Team for providing me with the resources and academic environment necessary to conduct this research and guidance in particularly challenging times, personally, academically, and professionally.

Finally, I extend my appreciation to all humanitarian professionals and researchers whose work in crisis management and logistics inspired this research. Their contributions to the field serve as a foundation for innovations that aim to improve aid distribution and emergency response efficiency.

This dissertation is as much a product of my efforts as it is a reflection of the invaluable support I have received. I hope it serves as a meaningful contribution for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers striving to enhance humanitarian operations through computational methods.

To all who have supported me in this journey, thank you!

Panagiotis Koilakos

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Abstract

Inefficient queue management in humanitarian operations can exacerbate aid delays, heighten social tension and entrench inequity, especially for vulnerable groups who cannot withstand long waits for registration or assistance. Addressing this challenge, the present study developed and validated a computational queue management framework that simultaneously enhances operational efficiency and upholds fairness in prioritising at-risk populations.

A discrete-event simulation modelled 1,000 synthetic beneficiaries across fourteen server configurations (service stations) and sixteen queuing policies, including FIFO, LIFO, M/M/C/k, Shortest Job First (SJF), Random Order Service (ROS), Round-Robin (RR), Multi-Level-Feedback-Queue (MLFQ) and 10 hybrid fairness-aware variants, within a modular architecture that supports low-resource deployment and future extensibility. Classical congestion measures (e.g., W_q , L_s , ρ) were integrated with a weighted multi-attribute equity score, while design requirements mandated bias mitigation, transparency and GDPR-aligned data handling.

Round-Robin emerges as the most balanced policy: with a configurable time slice, it halves the mean waiting time and lowers the composite cost by 40% relative to FIFO while sustaining more than 95% server utilisation in a ten-server scenario. However, the explainability and implementation of such a model in real-world queues are questionable. Where existing systems permit richer information, a utility-driven reinforcement-learning queue achieves the smoothest equity gradient, progressively shortening waits as vulnerability rises. Low-tech sites can nevertheless reduce vulnerable individuals' delays by overlaying colour-coded vulnerability tokens or simple deadline-based preemption on an otherwise FIFO process. Yet, equity can be further enhanced by combining different models, especially by introducing non-vulnerability-based preemption on vulnerability-aware policies to prevent starvation.

These findings give humanitarian agencies an evidence-based decision framework that shifts queue management from reactive crowd control to proactive, data-driven optim-

isation. By matching policy choice to digital maturity and monitoring fairness alongside throughput, organisations can register and serve more people, faster and more justly, without prohibitive resource demands, thereby advancing both operational and ethical mandates in crisis response.

Keywords: Queuing Theory, Queue Management, Algorithmic Fairness, Simulation, Discrete-Event Simulation, Humanitarian Logistics, Aid Distribution, Assistance Delivery, Registration Systems, Vulnerability Prioritisation

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Contents

List of Figures	x
List of Tables	xii
List of Abbreviations	xvi
1 Introduction	1
1.1 Context & Background	2
1.1.1 Queuing Theory & Applications	2
1.1.2 Challenges in Humanitarian Queue Management	3
1.2 Problem Statement	4
1.3 Aim & Objectives	5
1.3.1 Aim	5
1.3.2 Objectives	5
1.4 Research Questions	6
1.5 Scope & Limitations	7
1.6 Structure	8
2 Literature Review	9
2.1 Introduction to Queuing & Queue Management	9
2.1.1 Definitions & Foundations	9
2.1.2 Applications	14
2.2 Queuing in Humanitarian Environments	16
2.2.1 Unique Challenges of Humanitarian Queuing Systems	16
2.2.2 Existing Approaches to Humanitarian Queue Management	18
2.3 Literature Gaps	20
3 Research Considerations	22
3.1 Ethical Considerations	22
3.1.1 Data Protection & Privacy	22
3.1.2 Informed Consent	23

3.1.3	Bias, Fairness & Non-Discrimination	23
3.1.4	Psychological & Social Impact of Queuing Models	23
3.2	Professional Considerations	24
3.2.1	Compliance with the BCS Code of Conduct	24
3.2.2	Responsible Use	24
3.3	Risk Assessment	25
3.3.1	Ethical Risks	25
3.3.2	Risk Mitigation Strategies	25
3.4	Methodology	25
3.4.1	Research Design & Rationale	25
3.4.2	Data Collection & Analysis	26
3.4.3	Simulation & Modelling Approach	27
3.4.4	Evaluation Criteria & Metrics	27
3.4.5	Limitations	28
4	Arguments & Discussion	29
4.1	Problem & Requirement Analysis	29
4.2	Project Specifications	30
4.2.1	Functional Specifications	31
4.2.2	Non-Functional Specifications	34
4.2.3	Ethical Safeguards	34
4.3	Solution & Design	35
4.3.1	System Architecture	35
4.3.2	Simulation Workflow	36
4.3.3	Visualisation & Interpretation	37
4.3.4	Design Rationale	38
4.4	Artefact Development Process	39
4.5	Optimisation & Reflection	39
5	Evaluation	41
5.1	Evaluation Framework	41

5.2	Synthetic Data Overview	41
5.2.1	Data Generation & Simulation Parameters	41
5.2.2	Demographic & Vulnerability Profiles	42
5.3	Performance & Fairness Analysis by Model Type	46
5.3.1	Base Models	46
5.3.2	Hybrid Models	47
5.3.3	Priority-Based Models	48
5.3.4	Reinforcement-Inspired Models	48
5.3.5	Time-Slicing Models	49
5.3.6	Cross-model Observations	49
5.4	Comparative Performance Analysis	52
5.4.1	Performance Overview: 10-Server Configuration	52
5.4.2	Performance Comparison Strategy	54
5.4.3	Performance Comparison Results	57
5.5	Fairness Evaluation	58
5.6	Scalability & System Load Response	64
5.7	Limitations & Suggested Improvements	65
6	Learning	68
6.1	Research & Development Journey	68
6.2	Challenges Encountered	68
6.3	Solutions & Adaptations	69
6.4	Personal & Professional Development	69
6.5	Key Lessons Learned	70
7	Conclusion & Recommendations	71
8	References & Bibliography	74
A	Tables & Figures	86
B	Documentation Excerpt	105

List of Figures

1	Simulation workflow of the queuing artefact	37
2	Gender Distribution	42
3	Age Distribution	43
4	Vulnerability Score Distribution	43
5	Arrival Time Distribution	44
6	Transaction Time Distribution	45
7	Line plot of Average Waiting Time (W_q) per server for the First-In-First-Out (FIFO) model	50
8	Line plot of Average Queue Length (L_q) per server for the First-In-First-Out (FIFO) model	50
9	Line plot of Probability of Waiting (P_{wait}) per server for the First-In-First-Out (FIFO) model	51
10	Line plot of Probability of Waiting (P_{wait}) per server for the Patience-Aware Priority Queue (Patience Queue) model	51
11	Composite Score Scatter Plot	58
12	Heatmap of Average Waiting Time (W_q) by age cohort and vulnerability score for the First-In-First-Out (FIFO) model	60
13	Heatmap of Average Waiting Time (W_q) by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Shortest Job First (SJF) model	61
14	Heatmap of Average Waiting Time (W_q) by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Deadline-aware FIFO with vulnerability-based dynamic prioritisation (Deadline-aware First-In-First-Out (FIFO)) model	61
15	Heatmap of Average Waiting Time (W_q) by age cohort and vulnerability score for the FIFO with vulnerability-based pre-emption (First-In-First-Out (FIFO) with pre-emption) model	62

16	Heatmap of Average Waiting Time (W_q) by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Priority-Based Humanitarian Fairness Queue (Priority Queue) model	62
17	Heatmap of Average Waiting Time (W_q) by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Proportional Fair Queuing with Continuous Vulnerability-Based Priority (Proportional Fairness Queue) model	63
18	Heatmap of Average Waiting Time (W_q) by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Utility-Driven Scheduling (Reinforcement Learning (RL) Inspired) (RL Queue) model	63
19	Heatmap of average wait time by age cohort and vulnerability score for the RR model	64
20	Heatmap of Average Waiting Time (W_q) by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Community-Based Priority Queue (Community Queue) model	64

List of Tables

1	Overview of challenges in humanitarian queue management	4
2	Most studied queuing models	12
3	Most significant queuing metrics	13
4	Overview of applications of queuing theory across domains	16
5	High-level summary of Functional, Non-Functional, and Ethical Requirements	30
6	Summary statistics for the synthetic population	45
7	Aggregated performance metrics (10-server scenario)	53
8	Composite scores for each queuing model (0-1 and FIFO scales)	56
9	First-In-First-Out (FIFO): All Metrics	87
10	Last-In-First-Out (LIFO): All Metrics	88
11	Random Order Service (ROS): All Metrics	89
12	Shortest Job First (SJF): All Metrics	90
13	Deadline-aware FIFO with vulnerability-based dynamic prioritisation (Deadline-aware First-In-First-Out (FIFO)): All Metrics	91
14	FIFO with vulnerability-based pre-emption (First-In-First-Out (FIFO) with pre-emption): All Metrics	92
15	Priority-Based Humanitarian Fairness Queue (Priority Queue): All Metrics	93
16	Patience-Aware Priority Queue (Patience Queue): All Metrics	94
17	No-One-Left-Behind (Fairness-Triggered Priority Queue) (No-One-Left-Behind): All Metrics	95
18	Token Bucket with Vulnerability-Weighted Access Control (Token Queue): All Metrics	96
19	Community-Based Priority Queue (Community Queue): All Metrics	97
20	Fair Queuing with Continuous Vulnerability-Based Priority (Fair Queue): All Metrics	98

21	Proportional Fair Queuing with Continuous Vulnerability-Based Priority (Proportional Fairness Queue): All Metrics	99
22	Utility-Driven Scheduling (Reinforcement Learning (RL) Inspired) (RL Queue): All Metrics	100
23	Multi-Level Feedback Queue (MLFQ): All Metrics	101
24	Round Robin (RR): All Metrics	102
25	Min-max normalised Metrics (10-server scenario)	103
26	FIFO-relative normalised Metrics (10-server scenario)	104

List of Abbreviations

λ_{eff} Throughput	33, 46–49, 55
ρ Average Utilisation	34, 46–49, 55
B_T Total Busy Time	34, 46
I_T Total Idle Time	34, 49
L_q Average Queue Length	33, 49, 55
L_s Average Number in System	33, 49
P_{block} Probability of Blocking	33
P_{wait} Probability of Waiting	33, 50 ff., 55
W_q Average Waiting Time	33, 46–49, 55, 58 f.
W_s Average System Time	33, 58
First-In-First-Out (FIFO) with pre-emption FIFO with vulnerability-based pre-emption 47, 51, 57, 59, 65, 72 f.	
AI Artificial Intelligence	13, 18 f.
BCS British Computer Society The Chartered Institute for IT	22, 24
Community Queue Community-Based Priority Queue	32, 48, 51, 57, 60, 65
Deadline-aware FIFO Deadline-aware FIFO with vulnerability-based dynamic priorit- isation	47, 51, 57, 59, 65

Fair Queue Fair Queuing with Continuous Vulnerability-Based Priority	32, 48, 51, 57, 59, 65, 73
FCFS First-Come-First-Served	10 f., 19, 46, 71
FIFO First-In-First-Out	xiv, 2 f., 6, 10, 18 f., 26, 29, 31, 40 f., 46 ff., 50 ff., 54 f., 57 ff., 65, 71 ff.
GDPR General Data Protection Regulation	24, 73
LIFO Last-In-First-Out	31, 46, 50, 57 f., 65, 71
M/M/C/k Multi-Server Queuing Model	31, 46
MAUT Weighted-Additive Multi-Attribute Utility Theory	54
ML Machine Learning	19, 35
MLFQ Multi-Level Feedback Queue	33, 49 f., 57, 59, 65, 71
No-One-Left-Behind No-One-Left-Behind (Fairness-Triggered Priority Queue)	32, 47, 51, 57, 59, 65
Patience Queue Patience-Aware Priority Queue	32, 47, 51, 57, 59, 65, 71, 73
PII Personally Identifiable Information	22, 35
Priority Queue Priority-Based Humanitarian Fairness Queue	31, 47, 51, 57, 59, 73
Proportional Fairness Queue Proportional Fair Queuing with Continuous Vulnerability-Based Priority	48, 51, 57, 59, 65, 73
RL Queue Utility-Driven Scheduling (Reinforcement Learning (RL) Inspired)	32, 48, 50, 57, 59, 65, 71 f.
ROS Random Order Service	31, 46, 50, 57 f., 65, 71

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

RR Round Robin	11, 33, 49, 51, 57, 59, 64 f., 71 ff.
SJF Shortest Job First	11, 31, 46, 50, 57, 59, 64 f., 71 f.
SPT Shortest Processing Time	11
Token Queue Token Bucket with Vulnerability-Weighted Access Control	32, 48, 51, 57, 59, 65
UNHCR United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees	i, 20

1 Introduction

Effective queue management is critical in resource allocation, service efficiency, and fairness across multiple sectors, including healthcare, telecommunications, and logistics (Kleinrock, 1975; Shortle et al., 2017). While extensively applied in commercial and industrial domains, humanitarian contexts face unique challenges where queuing inefficiencies can result in delays in life-saving aid, social tensions, and inequitable service provision (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012; Kovács et al., 2007). Unlike conventional queue management, which primarily focuses on maximising throughput, humanitarian aid distribution must also account for ethical considerations and prioritise vulnerable populations (Gralla et al., 2014).

Despite advancements in data-driven logistics, most humanitarian queue management systems remain ad hoc, manually operated, and prone to inefficiencies (Van Wassenhove, 2006; Jahre et al., 2009). Existing systems struggle to balance operational efficiency with ethical considerations, often resulting in prolonged waiting times, inequitable aid distribution, and a lack of adaptive mechanisms (Sphere Association, 2018; Beamon et al., 2008). Long queues exacerbate food shortages, medical emergencies, and logistical failures, making access to essential resources unpredictable and unsustainable (Tatham et al., 2011).

Furthermore, systematic biases in aid distribution often lead to specific demographic groups facing disproportionate disadvantages, undermining the core humanitarian principle of impartiality (Barocas et al., 2023; O’Neil, 2016). Additionally, the absence of predictive optimisation techniques prevents aid agencies from dynamically adjusting to fluctuating demand, leaving them unprepared for sudden changes in crisis conditions (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012; Tambe, 2022).

This dissertation explores how queuing theory and algorithmic fairness principles can improve queue management in humanitarian contexts through computational simulation approaches. It proposes an adaptive, priority-based queuing system that dynamically alloc-

ates resources based on vulnerability, urgency, and fairness metrics. By incorporating data-driven insights, this research aims to enhance efficiency while upholding principles of equity and ethical accountability in humanitarian response settings (Madianou et al., 2015).

The following sections introduce queuing theory applications, the challenges of humanitarian queue management, and the research problem, aims, and scope of this dissertation.

1.1 Context & Background

1.1.1 Queuing Theory & Applications

As mentioned before, queuing theory, a branch of operations research and probability theory, provides mathematical models to optimise service efficiency and reduce congestion in waiting line systems (Kleinrock, 1975; Shortle et al., 2017). It has been extensively applied in telecommunications, healthcare, manufacturing, and transportation to enhance throughput and minimise delays (Larson, 1987). However, its adoption in humanitarian logistics remains underdeveloped, where queue mismanagement can lead to prolonged waiting times, aid shortages, and security risks (Tatham et al., 2011).

Several queuing models are commonly used in different settings, each with advantages and drawbacks:

FIFO The default approach in most humanitarian settings, simple but inefficient in prioritising high-risk individuals (Sphere Association, 2018; Gralla et al., 2014)

Priority Queuing Allocates higher priority to specific groups (e.g., medical emergencies, elderly individuals), but its implementation is prone to subjectivity and bias (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012; Beamon et al., 2008)

Randomised Selection Leads to unpredictability and fairness concerns

These models lack adaptive decision-making and real-time adjustments, making them ill-suited for dynamic humanitarian environments where demand surges and resource constraints fluctuate unpredictably.

1.1.2 Challenges in Humanitarian Queue Management

Inequitable Access to Aid FIFO-based queues often disadvantage at-risk individuals, including older persons at risk, people with disabilities, pregnant or lactating women, and non-native speakers, who may struggle to physically wait in long lines or navigate chaotic distribution processes (Joseph, 2020). Without structured prioritisation, those with greater urgency or vulnerability risk receiving aid too late (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012).

Operational and Logistical Bottlenecks Humanitarian organisations frequently contend with limited staff, inconsistent beneficiary identification, and manual queue oversight. Additionally, paper-based verification methods slow down registration processes, creating queues that last hours or even days (Tatham et al., 2011; UNHCR, 2012).

Security and Social Tensions Poorly managed queues escalate social tensions, leading to fights, queue-jumping, and security threats. Food distribution centres have sometimes witnessed riots due to perceived unfairness in aid allocation (Majumdar, 2007; MSF, 2016).

Lack of Predictive Optimisation Most current queuing systems do not leverage predictive models, leaving aid agencies unable to anticipate and adjust to fluctuating demand (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012; Tambe, 2022).

Given these challenges, there is a growing need for computationally optimised queue models that incorporate real-time prioritisation, fairness-aware metrics, and adaptive scheduling mechanisms.

Table 1: Overview of challenges in humanitarian queue management

Challenge	Description	Consequence
Inequitable Access	FIFO disadvantages vulnerable groups	Delayed aid
Operational Bottlenecks	Manual queue oversight	Long delays Inefficiencies
Security Risks	Poor queue design creates tension	Safety concerns
No Predictive Models	Lack of real-time optimisation	Inflexible response to crises

1.2 Problem Statement

As discussed previously, despite technological advancements, humanitarian queue management remains highly inefficient, inequitable, and prone to operational breakdowns (Van Wassenhove, 2006), with the existing system struggling to balance efficiency with ethical fairness, often leading to prolonged waiting times, inequitable aid distribution and an inability to adapt to real-time crises.

These challenges underscore the need for a holistic approach to queue management - one that integrates computational optimisation with ethical and operational constraints specific to humanitarian environments (Tambe, 2022). This dissertation proposes a computational queue management model that combines queuing theory with algorithmic fairness principles, allowing for dynamic prioritisation of aid recipients while ensuring equitable resource distribution.

By leveraging data-driven decision-making and real-time simulation techniques, the proposed model aims to enhance efficiency, reduce waiting times, and uphold ethical accountability in crisis response settings (Sphere Association, 2018).

1.3 Aim & Objectives

1.3.1 Aim

To develop and validate a computational queue management model for humanitarian registration and aid distribution activities that optimise operational efficiency and promote fairness in prioritising vulnerable populations.

1.3.2 Objectives

To achieve this overarching aim, the following high-level objectives have been identified:

1. Critically analyse existing queuing models, assess their applicability in humanitarian settings, and identify gaps and opportunities.
2. Design a computational queuing model incorporating vulnerability-based prioritisation and fairness-aware metrics.
3. Ensure that the developed simulation environment accurately models humanitarian operations' complexities and dynamic characteristics, including diverse beneficiary profiles.
4. Implement and test the queue management model using synthetic data that simulates real-world scenarios (C. Banks, 2010).
5. Provide actionable recommendations for implementing the proposed framework in real-world humanitarian operations.
6. Evaluate the performance of the proposed model against traditional queuing models, focusing on metrics measuring efficiency, fairness, and scalability.
7. Assess the ethical implications of the proposed framework, ensuring alignment with humanitarian principles and data protection standards.

1.4 Research Questions

The dissertation aims to answer a plethora of questions to guide the research process and ensure a comprehensive coverage of the research and problem space. As such, the following research questions have been formulated:

1. What are the key inefficiencies of existing queue management systems in humanitarian registration and aid distribution activities, and how do these inefficiencies affect resource allocation and waiting times?
2. How can queuing theory be adapted to address the distinct challenges of humanitarian aid distribution in crisis settings?
3. How does the proposed queue management framework compare in terms of operational efficiency and ethical alignment against traditional approaches, such as FIFO?
4. How can computational simulations of queuing theory be leveraged to model and anticipate bottlenecks in humanitarian registration and assistance delivery?
5. What algorithmic techniques can be employed to dynamically prioritise aid recipients based on urgency, vulnerability, and fairness?
6. How can fairness-aware algorithms be effectively integrated into humanitarian queuing models?
7. What practical challenges and ethical considerations arise when implementing computing-based queuing systems in humanitarian operations, and how can these be mitigated?

As such, the core research question can be formulated as:

“How can queuing theory, when applied through computing systems and simulations, enhance and optimise registration and assistance delivery activities in humanitarian contexts, particularly by improving resource allocation and reducing waiting times while ensuring ethical accountability to affected populations?”

1.5 Scope & Limitations

This research focuses on developing and validating a queue management framework specifically tailored for humanitarian aid distribution in crisis settings. The scope encompasses:

- Modelling humanitarian queuing systems, incorporating elements such as vulnerability prioritisation, resource constraints, ethical considerations, and the operational environment.
- Developing a simulation environment to test and validate the proposed framework.
- Analysing the performance using synthetic datasets that reflect typical humanitarian aid distribution scenarios.
- Conducting an ethical assessment of the proposed solution, including data protection, fairness, and transparency considerations.

However, the following scope limitations should be acknowledged:

- The research relies on synthetic data and simulations, which may not capture all nuances of real-world humanitarian operations.
- While the framework aims for generalisability, its effectiveness may vary across different types of humanitarian crises and cultural contexts.
- The study does not include field testing of the proposed solution due to logistical and ethical constraints.
- The framework does not address physical infrastructure constraints such as space or workstation allocation.
- Particular ethical trade-offs in prioritisation may arise, requiring stakeholder-specific adaptations.
- Long-term impacts and potential unintended consequences of implementing such a system in real-world settings are beyond the scope of this research.

1.6 Structure

The dissertation is structured as follows:

Section 1: Introduction This section details the research motivation and working context while outlining the project's aims, objectives, and scope.

Section 2: Literature Review This section critically reviews the available literature. It comprehensively discusses existing queuing theory and management literature, its applications in humanitarian contexts, and relevant technological advancements while intersecting with humanitarian logistics. It also discusses literature gaps.

Section 3: Ethical and Professional Considerations This section provides an in-depth discussion of the ethical and professional implications, including data protection, fairness, and alignment with humanitarian principles. The methodology, such as the research design and other artefact development components, is also discussed in this section.

Section 4: Arguments & Discussion This section presents the developed artefact, including but not limited to the used models, the simulation pipeline and the used validation techniques.

Section 5: Evaluation This section assesses the dissertation's effectiveness, efficiency and impact and related artefacts, critically reflecting the model's performance. It also suggests improvements and discusses the limitations of the simulation-based approach.

Section 6: Learning This section aids in reflecting on the search process and personal and professional growth while presenting challenges, solutions, and key lessons learned.

Section 7: Conclusion & Recommendations This section summarises key findings, acknowledges limitations and provides actionable recommendations for implementation while it presents potential areas of future research.

2 Literature Review

Understanding how queuing theory has been applied across different domains is essential to contextualising its role in humanitarian operations. The literature surrounding queuing models spans various disciplines, where performance optimisation is typically the primary goal. However, humanitarian contexts introduce unique constraints where ethical considerations, fairness, and vulnerability play central roles. This section critically surveys prior research, highlighting theoretical foundations, practical implementations, and the emerging discourse on fairness-aware scheduling models. It also identifies the gaps this dissertation aims to address.

2.1 Introduction to Queuing & Queue Management

Queuing theory, or waiting line theory, is a branch of operations research and probability theory that provides a mathematical framework for analysing waiting lines, optimising service efficiency, and minimising congestion. It aims to model real-world systems where demand for service exceeds immediate capacity, requiring entities, such as customers or requests, to form queues (Kleinrock, 1975). These models help evaluate key performance metrics such as average queue length, system utilisation, and expected waiting time (Shortle et al., 2017).

2.1.1 Definitions & Foundations

At its core, queuing theory aims to understand and predict various aspects of waiting lines, such as average waiting time, queue length, server utilisation, and the probability of the system being in a particular state. The primary goal is to help in system design, resource allocation, and the formulation of service policies to balance service quality and resource efficiency (Newell, 1982).

The genesis of queuing theory can be traced back to the pioneering work of Agner Krarup Erlang, a Danish mathematician. In the early 20th century, Erlang studied telephone traffic

congestion for the Copenhagen Telephone Exchange (Erlang, n.d.). His work led to the development of several fundamental formulas, including the Erlang B and Erlang C formulas, which are still widely used today in telecommunications and various other industries to determine the number of servers required to meet a specified service level target, such as the probability of a call being blocked or delayed (Levy, 1983). Erlang's contributions laid the foundation for the modern queuing theory (Aksin et al., 2007).

The fundamental structure of a queuing system consists of the following components:

Arrival Process The arrival process describes how entities enter the system. This process is often characterised by the inter-arrival time distribution, which specifies the time between successive arrivals. The most commonly used distribution is the Poisson distribution, characterised by its memoryless property, where events occur independently and at a constant average rate (Kleinrock, 1975). However, arrivals may not always follow a Poisson process in real-world systems. More complex models may incorporate non-stationary arrival processes, where the arrival rate varies over time due to seasonality, trends, or external events (Tatham et al., 2011; Holguín-Veras et al., 2012).

Service Process/Mechanism The service process describes the time it takes for an entity to be served. The service process is characterised by the service time distribution (Shortle et al., 2017). Common distributions used to model service times include the exponential, standard, and deterministic (constant) distributions. In some queuing systems, the service time may depend on the type of entity or the server providing the service (Gralla et al., 2014; Green, 2006).

Queue Discipline The rules dictating the order of service (Harchol-Balter, 2013). The queue discipline specifies the order in which entities are selected for service from the queue. Several queue disciplines are commonly used in practice (Shortle et al., 2017):

- **First-Come-First-Served (FCFS):** Also known as FIFO, is the simplest and most commonly used queue discipline. Entities are served in the order they

arrive. FCFS is generally considered fair and easy to implement, but it may not be optimal in minimising average waiting time or maximising throughput (Conway et al., 1967).

- **Priority Queuing:** Entities are assigned priorities, and those with higher priorities are served before those with lower priorities. Priorities can be static, assigned at arrival based on factors such as customer status or urgency, or dynamic, changing over time based on factors such as waiting time or the number of entities in the queue (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012). Priority queuing can effectively reduce waiting times for high-priority entities but can also lead to starvation, where low-priority entities are never served (Kleinrock, 1975).
- **Shortest Job First (SJF):** Also known as Shortest Processing Time (SPT), is a queueing model where entities with shorter service times are served first. This discipline minimises the average waiting time but can lead to starvation for entities with longer service times (Conway et al., 1967).
- **Round Robin (RR):** Each entity receives a fixed amount of service time in turn. If an entity's service is not completed within its time slice, it is returned to the end of the queue. This discipline is commonly used in computer systems and time-sharing environments to provide fair access to resources (Allen, 1990).

Number of Servers The number of servers specifies the number of parallel servers available to provide service. A single-server system has one server, while a multi-server system has multiple servers. Multi-server systems are generally more efficient than single-server systems, as they can handle a higher volume of traffic (Shortle et al., 2017). However, multi-server systems also require more resources and may be more complex to manage.

System Capacity The system capacity specifies the maximum number of entities in the system at any given time, including those being served and those waiting in the queue. Systems with finite capacity may experience blocking, where arriving entities are turned away if the system is full (Ancker et al., 1963). The system capacity

can significantly impact the queuing system's performance, especially when the arrival rate is high (Newell, 1982).

Mathematical Notations & Performance Metrics

Mathematically, queuing models are categorised using Kendall's notation (A/B/C), where A represents the arrival process, B denotes the service time distribution, and C specifies the number of service channels (Shortle et al., 2017). The most widely studied models include:

Table 2: Most studied queuing models

Model	Description
M/M/1	Single-server queue with Poisson arrivals and exponential service times
M/M/c	Multi-server system where multiple servers operate in parallel
M/M/c/k	Multi-server system with finite capacity where multiple servers operate in parallel and blocking is implemented
M/G/1	Single-server queue with a general service time distribution ¹
G/G/1	A general queuing model where both the arrival process and service process follow an arbitrary distribution ¹

¹ (Shortle et al., 2017; Taha, 2017)

Queuing models are assessed using performance metrics such as Little's Law, which establishes the relationship between system length (L), arrival rate (λ), and waiting time (W) as $L = \lambda W$ with the system length being equal to the arrival rate multiplied by the waiting time.

This formula is widely applicable across different queuing models and helps in capacity planning and efficiency optimisation (Little, 1961), with Little's Law holding true for a wide range of queuing systems, regardless of the specific arrival process, service time distribution, or queue discipline.

With that in mind, the performance metrics of a queuing system can be further expanded with a broader variety of metrics:

Table 3: Most significant queuing metrics

Metric	Description
Average Waiting Time (W_q)	The mean time an entity spends waiting in the queue before being served
Average System Time (W_s)	The mean time an entity spends in the system (waiting and being served)
Average Number in System (L_s)	The mean number of entities in the system (waiting and being served)
Average Utilisation (ρ)	The proportion of time that the servers are busy. It is calculated as the arrival rate divided by the service rate
Probability of Waiting (P_{wait})	The probability that an arriving entity will have to wait in the queue
Probability of Blocking (P_{block})	The probability that an arriving entity will be turned away due to the system being full (in systems with finite capacity)

In practical applications, queuing systems are often more complex, incorporating batch arrivals, time-dependent service rates, and interconnected queuing networks. To handle such complexities, modern queue management integrates predictive analytics, real-time monitoring, and Artificial Intelligence (AI)-driven decision-making (Koole et al., 2002).

Modern queuing theory has evolved to incorporate multi-class queuing models, where different customer categories experience distinct service priorities and constraints (Gans et al., 2003; Harchol-Balter, 2013).

Moreover, modern queue management incorporates customer flow forecasting, automated ticketing systems, AI-driven scheduling, and mobile queueing solutions (Gans et al., 2003; Tamba, 2022). Simulation-based queue analysis, where queuing scenarios are tested under

different constraints, is widely used in queue optimisation in different disciplines (Liu et al., 2019).

Modern queue management also incorporates fairness-aware queuing models, which aim to reduce biases and ensure equitable access to resources (Barocas et al., 2023). These models use algorithms that account for demographic factors, urgency levels, and historical wait times to adjust queue orders dynamically (Liu et al., 2019).

2.1.2 Applications

Queuing theory and queue management are vital in optimising service delivery and resource allocation across numerous industries. These applications range from healthcare and telecommunications to manufacturing and smart cities, demonstrating the versatility and importance of queue management systems in both the public and private sectors (Harchol-Balter, 2013; Shortle et al., 2017).

In healthcare and emergency services, queuing models are extensively used to manage patient flow, reduce wait times, and optimise hospital resources (Green, 2006; Fomundam et al., 2007; Cayirli et al., 2003), including during emergency and triage situations where severity-based prioritisation prevents life-threatening delays (Hulshof et al., 2012; Tambe, 2022). Similarly, surgical scheduling models use queuing principles to improve operating room utilisation and minimise delays (Koole et al., 2002), while ambulance dispatching services enhance response times by dynamically adjusting route prioritisation (Gans et al., 2003).

In telecommunications, queuing theory is essential for traffic congestion management, data packet transmission, and bandwidth allocation (Harchol-Balter, 2013; Daigle, 2005). Internet routers, cloud computing systems, and 5G networks implement priority queuing algorithms to handle high data traffic efficiently, balance computing loads dynamically, and minimise network latency (Andrews et al., 2014; Jain and Paul, 2013; Liu et al., 2019). Queuing theory is also fundamental to designing and analysing computer systems, enhancing CPU scheduling, memory allocation and network traffic flow (Allen, 1990).

Queuing models also play a crucial role in manufacturing and supply chain logistics, where efficient workflow management is necessary to minimise delays and optimise production output (Hopp et al., 2008). Factory assembly lines implement M/M/c queue models to balance workloads across multiple production stations, reducing idle times and increasing efficiency (Herrmann et al., 2006; Papadopoulos et al., 2009), while warehousing and inventory systems apply queuing models for demand forecasting and real-time stock replenishment, ensuring smooth logistics operations (Osorio et al., 2013).

Queuing models are equally fundamental to traffic congestion management, public transit optimisation, and airport operations (Shortle et al., 2017). Queuing models are used with real-time data for adaptive traffic signal control, reducing vehicle congestion (Osorio et al., 2013), in queuing algorithms to optimise train scheduling (Hansen, 2002), and in queuing-based runway scheduling to efficiently manage aircraft take-off and landing sequences (Koole et al., 2002; Barnhart et al., 2003).

Moreover, retail businesses and customer service centres leverage queuing systems to manage customer flow, optimise service speed, and enhance user experience (Gans et al., 2003). Such systems are used in supermarket self-checkouts to distribute customers evenly, reducing congestion (Harchol-Balter, 2013), during store layout design to minimise congestion and maximise customer flow (Larson, 1987) and in call centres to route customers dynamically based on agent availability, minimising wait times (Koole et al., 2002; Ibrahim, 2018).

Queuing theory also plays a crucial role in banking and financial services, with teller queuing systems in physical branches directly affecting customer satisfaction and operational efficiency (Gans et al., 2003; Ibrahim, 2018; Koole et al., 2002). Digital banking platforms employ load balancing and transaction queuing models to handle online banking requests efficiently, mitigating bottlenecks during high-traffic periods (Liu et al., 2019).

Finally, government agencies use queuing models to improve passport issuance, visa processing, vehicle registration, and tax collection services (Koole et al., 2002), but also during disaster relief, ensuring that assistance reaches affected populations efficiently

(Holguín-Veras et al., 2012).

Table 4: Overview of applications of queuing theory across domains

Sector	Common Models Used	Primary Objectives
Healthcare	M/M/1, Priority Queues	Reduce patient wait times Triage critical cases
Aviation	Multi-server, Time-sliced	Minimize runway delays Optimise air traffic
Retail	FIFO, Multi-channel	Improve customer flow Improve service efficiency
Call Centres	M/M/c, Dynamic Routing	Balance load Reduce abandonment rates
Humanitarian Logistics	Fair Queuing, Priority Models	Ensure equitable access Protect vulnerable populations

¹ (Fomundam et al., 2007; Mustafa, 2015; Li, 2024; Peter et al., 2021)

2.2 Queuing & Queue Management in Humanitarian Environments

2.2.1 Unique Challenges of Humanitarian Queuing Systems

Queue management in humanitarian environments presents distinct challenges compared to traditional queuing systems in commercial or industrial settings. Unlike structured service environments like retail or healthcare, humanitarian queuing systems must function under highly uncertain, volatile, and resource-constrained conditions. The presence of displaced populations, urgent needs, and logistical complexities further complicate the design and operation of efficient queue management strategies (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012).

One of the most significant challenges in humanitarian queuing is the unpredictable nature of demand, where sudden surges due to conflict, natural disasters, or food shortages can overwhelm existing queue management systems. Unlike commercial environments where demand forecasting models can be optimised based on historical data, humanitarian queues

require adaptive, real-time queue management systems to respond effectively to fluctuating demand (Van Wassenhove, 2006).

Moreover, funding for humanitarian aid is typically limited and may not always align with the scale of the crisis. As such, limited staffing, space, and infrastructure restrict queue efficiency in such operations. Many aid distribution centres operate in remote or conflict-affected regions where basic infrastructure, such as electricity, internet connectivity, and transport networks, is insufficient or non-existent (Sphere Association, 2018). Due to the often lack of digital infrastructure, prioritisation must rely on manual decision-making, leading to inefficiencies and potential biases in service delivery (Tatham et al., 2011).

Humanitarian queuing systems must also account for diverse beneficiary vulnerability levels. The older or disabled individuals, pregnant women, and unaccompanied minors often require prioritised access to life-sustaining resources such as food, medical care, and shelter (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012). However, implementing priority-based queuing in humanitarian settings is challenging due to the lack of centralised databases and identity verification systems (Glasman, 2019). Moreover, displaced individuals lack formal identification, making it challenging to assess vulnerability systematically.

Additionally, cultural and social factors influence queue behaviour, requiring localised solutions that respect community norms while ensuring equitable service allocation (Van Wassenhove, 2006; IFRC, 2016). Managing such a diverse group requires careful consideration of prioritisation strategies that balance fairness with the need to address urgent cases quickly.

Another difference between humanitarian and commercial queues is the heightened concern for security. Poorly managed queues can lead to frustration, conflict, and even violence, particularly when access to essential resources is perceived as unfair. Studies on humanitarian logistics indicate that poor queuing mechanisms have led to riots and security incidents in food distribution centres (Sphere Association, 2018; Tatham et al., 2011).

Additionally, the psychological state of individuals in humanitarian queues is often fragile due to the trauma and stress of the crisis. Long wait times, uncertainty about resource avail-

ability, and perceived unfairness in queue management can exacerbate psychological distress. In humanitarian contexts, queue management is about efficiency, ensuring fairness and upholding ethical standards. Unlike commercial queue management, humanitarian queues must adhere to the ethical imperatives of fairness, transparency, and impartiality (Barocas et al., 2023; Sphere Association, 2018; Liu et al., 2019).

Another contrast is that humanitarian contexts often suffer from incomplete or inconsistent data on aid recipients, preventing the implementation of predictive queuing models. Aid organisations struggle to allocate resources efficiently without accurate data on past demand trends. The lack of interoperability between different humanitarian agencies further compounds this issue (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012).

Moreover, humanitarian operations typically involve multiple stakeholders, including NGOs, local governments, and international organisations. Coordinating queue management across these different actors can be highly challenging, with each organisation having its own priorities, procedures, and systems, making it challenging to implement a unified and consistent approach to queue management across different aid distribution points.

Finally, while AI-driven queue management and biometric verification systems have been widely adopted in commercial settings, their implementation in humanitarian environments remains limited due to technological and financial constraints (Liu et al., 2019). Many displaced populations lack the digital literacy or access to technological equipment, preventing them from using mobile-based digital appointment scheduling (Hironde, 2025). Blockchain-based identity verification has been proposed to streamline queue prioritisation and prevent fraud in aid distribution, but its adoption remains limited due to infrastructure challenges (WFP, 2025).

2.2.2 Existing Approaches to Humanitarian Queue Management

Over the years, different approaches have been implemented to address the unique challenges of humanitarian queuing systems. These approaches range from traditional FIFO models to more sophisticated data-driven and AI-enhanced queue management strategies.

The most widely used queuing system in humanitarian settings is the FCFS (also known as FIFO) model. This approach ensures that aid recipients are served in the order they arrive, creating an ostensibly fair but highly inefficient queue structure. While FCFS eliminates the need for subjective prioritisation, it fails to account for differences in vulnerability levels, leading to inequitable service distribution where high-risk groups may experience dangerous delays (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012).

To address the shortcomings of FCFS, priority-based queuing models have been introduced in various humanitarian contexts. These systems allocate service priority based on predefined vulnerability criteria (Tatham et al., 2011; Beamon et al., 2008). Despite their advantages, priority-based models face significant implementation challenges, particularly when verifying eligibility and preventing fraud. Additionally, the subjectivity in assessing priority groups can introduce biases, resulting in perceptions of unfairness or corruption (Glasman, 2019).

A more structured approach to humanitarian queue management uses token-based queuing systems, where beneficiaries receive numbered tokens upon arrival to secure their place in line. This system helps reduce disorderly queues and prevent crowding, thereby improving security and efficiency (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012).

Appointment-based systems have also gained traction in some humanitarian operations, allowing aid recipients to schedule specific time slots for service. This approach can significantly reduce on-site waiting times and help manage crowd sizes. However, it may be challenging to implement in rapidly changing crisis environments and can disadvantage those without reliable access to communication channels for booking appointments (Tatham et al., 2011).

With the recent technological advancements, AI and Machine Learning (ML) algorithms are increasingly being explored as tools for optimising queue management in humanitarian settings. AI-based queuing systems can dynamically adjust service order based on real-time factors such as queue length, crowd density, and recipient urgency levels (Tambe, 2022; WFP, 2025; Koole et al., 2002). However, these approaches require robust data

collection, digital infrastructure, and ethical considerations to avoid black-box solutions that inadvertently exclude vulnerable populations (Barocas et al., 2023).

Somewhat more recent innovations in humanitarian logistics include biometric identification and blockchain-based queue management. Organisations such as the World Food Programme (WFP) and UNHCR have successfully implemented biometric verification systems to prevent duplicate aid collection and improve transparency in queue prioritisation (WFP, 2025; UNHCR, 2022a; Glasman, 2019). These technologies help mitigate fraud and increase accountability, but pose privacy concerns and data security risks, particularly in politically unstable regions.

Moreover, community-driven queuing models have proven more effective in some contexts than externally imposed systems (Sphere Association, 2018). Studies have shown that when queue prioritisation is locally managed, there is greater trust in the fairness of the process, resulting in higher compliance and reduced queue-related conflicts (Van Wassenhove, 2006). However, community-driven approaches require strong governance mechanisms to prevent favouritism and reinforce equitable service delivery (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012).

Finally, integrated approaches that combine multiple queue management strategies have also been developed, aiming to balance efficiency, fairness, and flexibility in complex humanitarian environments (Gralla et al., 2014).

2.3 Literature Gaps

Despite the advancements in queuing theory and queue management strategies, significant gaps remain in applying these models to humanitarian settings. Current research primarily focuses on commercial and industrial applications, with limited studies addressing the unique challenges of the distribution of humanitarian assistance, refugee camps, and disaster relief operations (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012; Van Wassenhove, 2006). These gaps hinder developing robust, scalable, and equitable queuing solutions tailored for crisis environments.

Most queuing models have been developed for structured environments where demand and service capacity are relatively predictable. However, humanitarian settings feature highly volatile demand surges, resource constraints, and demographic diversity, requiring queuing models that dynamically adapt to fluctuating crisis conditions (Tatham et al., 2011; Kovács et al., 2007). Existing research lacks comprehensive simulations and case studies analysing queue dynamics in unstable environments.

Moreover, equity and fairness-aware queuing models have not been sufficiently incorporated into existing queue optimisation strategies (Barocas et al., 2023; O’Neil, 2016). Many current queuing mechanisms prioritise efficiency over fairness, potentially exacerbating systemic inequalities in aid distribution (Glasman, 2019). Research is needed to explore how algorithmic bias can be mitigated in queue prioritisation systems and to develop frameworks that ensure equitable access for vulnerable groups.

With humanitarian operations often involving multiple organisations operating in parallel (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012), there is a need for inter-agency coordination frameworks that facilitate data-sharing, interoperability, and queue harmonisation among different stakeholders, thus potentially avoiding inconsistent queuing protocols and prolonged wait times (Sphere Association, 2018).

On the psychological front, only a few studies address the long-term social, economic, and psychological impacts of queuing mechanisms in humanitarian contexts (Van Wassenhove, 2006). Future research should examine how prolonged waiting experiences affect trust in humanitarian institutions, community stability, and recipient dignity (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012). Incorporating qualitative studies and recipient feedback mechanisms can provide deeper insights into the human-centred dimensions of queue management in crisis scenarios (Tatham et al., 2011).

3 Ethical, Professional & Methodological Considerations

Ethical considerations are paramount in research, especially when involving vulnerable populations in humanitarian settings. Designing and implementing a queue management system in humanitarian contexts involves more than just throughput optimisation; it touches on sensitive ethical questions that can significantly impact vulnerable populations. Such systems handle personal data and may shape life-critical decisions, so developers and researchers must be aware of the societal, cultural, and personal implications. In addition, professional guidelines, such as the British Computer Society The Chartered Institute for IT (BCS) Code of Conduct (BCS, 2022), demand a strong commitment to transparency, accountability, and ongoing ethical review. The following sections examine the key ethical considerations for this research. *All dissertations submitted to the University of Essex, including the present, have obtained ethical approval.*

3.1 Ethical Considerations

3.1.1 Data Protection & Privacy

Data protection and privacy are critical when designing or assessing queue management systems in humanitarian contexts, particularly due to the heightened vulnerability of the populations served (UNHCR, 2022b). Even when synthetic datasets are used, safeguarding measures must be in place to prevent exposure or misuse of Personally Identifiable Information (PII) (WFP, 2016; EU, 2016; EDPS, 2025). In addition, employing secure version control and repositories with strict permission settings helps block unauthorised edits or downloads, thereby reinforcing data integrity (Ballout et al., 2022). Although no direct human participants are involved in this research, a thorough ethical assessment remains vital to uphold best practices. All research artefacts must be stored on password-protected devices, with backups maintained in encrypted environments. Data are retained for the duration of the research plus six months, after which they are securely deleted to ensure complete compliance with institutional and ethical requirements.

3.1.2 Informed Consent

This dissertation does not involve direct interactions with human participants, and no publicly or privately available (primary or secondary) datasets are used (Oates et al., 2021). Regardless, any inferred observations should assess the ethical character of the source, especially due to the fact that in humanitarian contexts, displaced individuals often lack the autonomy or resources to give fully informed, voluntary consent (UNHCR, 2024a). Where possible, pre-approved and well-documented datasets minimise ethical ambiguities (ACM, 2018).

3.1.3 Bias, Fairness & Non-Discrimination

Modern queue management simulations incorporate fairness metrics alongside traditional measures of throughput or average wait time (Barocas et al., 2023). Using Python, developers can implement parity-based checks to detect whether certain groups face systematically longer queues (O’Neil, 2016). Vulnerable populations should receive priority if they face disproportionate risks. Testing the model on edge-case scenarios reveals potential biases early (Glasman, 2019). Fairness in queue allocation not only reduces discrimination but also aligns with humanitarian principles of impartiality and non-discrimination (Larson, 1987). Continuous refinement, aided by real-time feedback loops, guards against algorithmic drift that could disadvantage specific demographics (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012) despite seemingly improving queuing efficiencies.

3.1.4 Psychological & Social Impact of Queuing Models

Queueing is a social phenomenon as much as a logistical one; especially in humanitarian or crisis contexts, it can amplify stress, anxiety, and even conflict (Zhou et al., 2008). Individuals forced to wait for critical resources often perceive delays as a personal injustice, which may undermine trust in aid agencies. Transparent information provision about approximate wait times and detailed prioritisation criteria can mitigate frustration (Tatham et al., 2011). Additionally, factoring community norms, such as gender, segregated lines or local leadership structures, into the queue’s design can enhance social acceptance (Van Wassenhove, 2006). Ultimately, psychologically informed queue management respects

crisis-affected individuals' dignity and emotional well-being.

3.2 Professional Considerations

3.2.1 Compliance with the BCS Code of Conduct

The BCS Code of Conduct promotes integrity, competence, and alignment with the public interest (BCS, 2022). In humanitarian contexts, these guidelines have heightened importance due to the stakes involved; queue management outcomes might directly affect life-sustaining services. Researchers and developers must thoroughly document assumptions and potential conflicts of interest, revealing any organisational or funding biases (ACM, 2018). Additionally, abiding by legal and regulatory frameworks such as General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) ensures that data handling respects personal rights and dignity (WFP, 2016; UNHCR, 2022b). By prioritising these principles, queue management systems uphold values of equity, transparency, and protection for vulnerable populations (Tambe, 2022).

3.2.2 Responsible Use

Responsible use implies a broad ethical stance on how queue management results are interpreted, communicated, and deployed (Glasman, 2019). This includes offering clear documentation that outlines the algorithm's intent and scope and clarifying any assumptions or constraints (O'Neil, 2016). Conducting routine stress tests allows developers to see how the system adapts to surges in demand or sudden demographic shifts. Engaging local communities and frontline personnel in pilot runs can highlight overlooked cultural or social factors (Tatham et al., 2011). Ultimately, responsible use may entail suspending or recalibrating the system if it risks exacerbating inequities or causing harm, reinforcing the notion that technology should remain subordinate to humanitarian objectives (ACM, 2018).

3.3 Risk Assessment and Mitigation Strategies

3.3.1 Ethical Risks

Ethical risks in queue management include data breaches, which could expose the personal details of displaced persons to hostile actors (O’Neil, 2016). Algorithmic bias may inadvertently sideline specific groups, such as older adults or those with language barriers (Barocas et al., 2023; Deller, 2018). Additionally, a lack of transparency might undermine trust among recipients, triggering anger and mistrust in camp settings (Larson, 1987). Over time, if the system remains static, model drift could lead to outdated allocations, disadvantaging the most in-need populations (Fomundam et al., 2007).

3.3.2 Risk Mitigation Strategies

A multifaceted approach helps minimise these risks. Technical safeguards include secure repositories with strict user permissions and routine code reviews (ISO, 2022). Algorithmic transparency, such as displaying fairness metrics for different demographic categories, promotes trust and highlights any emerging imbalances (Tambe, 2022). Community engagement is equally vital; even though not used in this dissertation due to its experimental nature, it must be employed during field roll-out (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012). Regularly updating algorithms as crisis conditions evolve mitigates model drift, while fallback mechanisms ensure that operations can continue if automated systems fail (Joseph, 2020). These measures align with recognised ethical guidelines and ensure that humanitarian technology upholds its core mission of saving lives and alleviating suffering (ACM, 2018).

3.4 Methodology

3.4.1 Research Design & Rationale

This study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining quantitative simulation modelling with qualitative ethical analysis to address the complex challenges of humanitarian queue management. The research emphasises in practical problem-solving and integrating diverse methodological approaches, such as data-driven simulations in controlled test-

ing environments, which minimise variability while maintaining analytical rigour (Tambe, 2022). This approach allows for a comprehensive examination of both the operational efficiency and ethical implications of queue management strategies in humanitarian contexts.

The rationale for this design stems from the multifaceted nature of humanitarian queuing challenges, which encompass technical, social, and ethical dimensions. Quantitative modelling enables the systematic evaluation of queue performance metrics. At the same time, qualitative ethical analysis ensures that the proposed solutions align with humanitarian principles and consider the diverse needs of affected populations.

3.4.2 Data Collection & Analysis

Given the absence of standardised humanitarian queue datasets, this research relies on synthetically generated data to simulate refugee camp queues, food distribution lines, and emergency medical service flows (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012). The dataset is constructed based on historical queuing parameters, observed service demand trends, and priority-based access models documented in humanitarian logistics literature.

The data analysis focuses on:

Queue Performance Metrics Metrics, such as mean waiting time, queue length, and service completion rates (Tatham et al., 2011), will be used to assess queuing performance and efficiency

Fairness Metrics Disparities in service access across vulnerability groups (Barocas et al., 2023)

Comparative Model Evaluation FIFO vs. priority-based queue models (Liu et al., 2019)

For a complete analysis, please refer to Section 5.

Simulations are executed using Python-based queuing to model dynamic queue conditions (Koole et al., 2002). Data visualisation tools are employed to interpret results effectively.

3.4.3 Simulation & Modelling Approach

The simulation framework models queue operations under varying crisis scenarios. Each simulation run is designed to replicate queue congestion scenarios under different priority-based intervention mechanisms. The model validation process ensures that results are robust, statistically significant, and applicable to real-world humanitarian settings (Tambe, 2022).

The simulation is designed to capture the stochastic nature of humanitarian operations and allows for exploring “what-if” scenarios (C. Banks, 2010). The model incorporates agent-based modelling elements to represent aid recipients’ diverse characteristics and behaviours. This approach enables a more nuanced representation of queue dynamics, accounting for factors such as vulnerability levels, patience thresholds, and individuals’ decision-making processes within the queue.

3.4.4 Evaluation Criteria & Metrics

The effectiveness of queue management strategies is evaluated using a multi-criteria framework that balances operational efficiency with ethical considerations. Key performance indicators include:

- Mean waiting time, queue length, and system utilisation (Little, 1961)
- Fairness metrics, to ensure proportional access across vulnerable populations (Sphere Association, 2018)
- Integrated scalability metrics, to assess the model’s ability to handle fluctuating demand surges (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012)
- Queuing Length

A comparative analysis is conducted between traditional and priority-based queuing, ensuring efficiency and ethical considerations are accounted for.

3.4.5 Limitations

While the chosen methodology offers a comprehensive approach to studying humanitarian queue management, several limitations must be acknowledged:

Data limitations While modelled after real-world distributions, synthetic datasets cannot fully capture all situational nuances

Ethical Trade-offs Queue fairness models may involve prioritisation challenges that are difficult to resolve algorithmically (Barocas et al., 2023). The ethical framework used may not encompass all relevant moral considerations (O’Neil, 2016)

Generalisation & Simplification Issues While designed to be comprehensive, the simulation model necessarily simplifies the complex and often chaotic nature of humanitarian crises. Model outcomes may not directly translate to all humanitarian settings due to region-specific socio-cultural dynamics (Glasman, 2019; Van Wassenhove, 2006; Holguín-Veras et al., 2012)

Technological barriers The proposed queue management strategies assume a level of technological infrastructure that is not always available in humanitarian settings, potentially limiting their applicability in some contexts (Sandvik et al., 2014)

4 Arguments & Discussion

The design, implementation, and ethical evaluation of the simulation artefact are guided by a synthesis of humanitarian objectives and computational constraints. This section presents a structured analysis of how the simulation artefact was developed, validated, and interpreted, offering both technical justification and ethical reflection, outlining the key problem space and system requirements before delving into the technical architecture, solution design, and implementation details. The latter half of the section evaluates the rationale behind design decisions and reflects on the trade-offs between different requirements.

4.1 Problem & Requirement Analysis

Humanitarian queue management poses a distinct challenge of operational constraints and moral imperatives. Prolonged waiting times, inequitable access to services, and the inability to adapt to dynamic conditions highlight the inadequacy of traditional queuing systems such as FIFO.

Although the implemented simulation framework does not have direct end-users in its current experimental form, it has been designed to enable future applications to real-world humanitarian scenarios. Should synthetic data be replaced with field-collected datasets, the system could be used to evaluate which queuing models perform best under specific contextual constraints.

The following table presents a summarised requirement analysis based on project goals and ethical-operational considerations.

Table 5: High-level summary of Functional, Non-Functional, and Ethical Requirements

Requirement Type	Requirement Description
Functional	Simulate multiple queuing strategies
Functional	Accept synthetic data inputs representing beneficiary profiles
Functional	Gather & compare output performance metrics
Functional	Allow configurable queue scenarios
Non-Functional	Operable in low-resource computing environments
Non-Functional	Modular architecture supporting future extension
Non-Functional	Reproducible outputs with standardised configuration management
Ethical	Avoid bias against vulnerable individuals; support fairness auditing
Ethical	Enable transparent logic for queue ordering and decision criteria

This table reflects a high-level synthesis of inferred requirements. Due to this work’s experimental and simulation-based nature, formal requirement gathering from stakeholders was beyond the scope of this dissertation.

This requirements mapping was driven by the project’s dual objective: producing a computationally sound simulation while upholding humanitarian values of impartiality and accountability. These informed both the design and the metrics used during experimentation, ensuring that technical choices aligned with broader ethical expectations (Holguín-Veras et al., 2012; Barocas et al., 2023; Sphere Association, 2018; Sandvik et al., 2014).

4.2 Project Specifications

Building upon the requirements outlined in Section 4.1, this section describes the technical and architectural specifications that guided the development of the simulation artefact. The goal was to create a modular, ethically grounded, and computationally efficient system capable of evaluating varying queuing strategies under humanitarian conditions (Van Wassenhove, 2006).

Such simulation tools have been validated in humanitarian logistics as effective for planning and system optimisation under uncertainty (Santos et al., 2018).

4.2.1 Functional Specifications

The simulation system was implemented to support multiple queuing models (Huang et al., 2015; McCoy et al., 2014; Robertson et al., 2024; Harchol-Balter, 2013; Shortle et al., 2017) specifically:

1. Base Models

First-In First-Out (FIFO) Individuals are served strictly in the order they arrive (Shortle et al., 2017).

Last-In-First-Out (LIFO) The most recently arrived individual is served first, often used in stack-based systems or when recency reflects urgency (Shortle et al., 2017).

Multi-Server Queuing Model (M/M/C/k) For the purpose of this dissertation, M/M/C/k behaves precisely the same as FIFO (Shortle et al., 2017).

Random Order Service (ROS) Individuals are selected for service randomly from the queue (Shortle et al., 2017).

Shortest Job First (SJF) The individual with the shortest estimated service time is explicitly prioritised (Shortle et al., 2017).

2. Hybrid Models

Deadline-aware FIFO with vulnerability-based dynamic prioritisation A FIFO-based queue that dynamically reorders individuals before service based on whether they have waited too long and/or are vulnerable, using a three-level priority system (Shortle et al., 2017).

FIFO with vulnerability-based pre-emption A standard FIFO queue that pre-emptively inserts highly vulnerable individuals at the front of the queue upon arrival (Shortle et al., 2017).

Priority-Based Humanitarian Fairness Queue (Priority Queue) Implements a fair-

ness formula that combines vulnerability scores with fixed modifiers to assign continuous priority levels (Van Wassenhove, 2006).

Patience-Aware Priority Queue (Patience Queue) Prioritises individuals based on an estimated patience score, assuming that more vulnerable individuals are less tolerant to waiting and those with longer service needs are slightly more tolerant (Shortle et al., 2017).

No-One-Left-Behind (Fairness-Triggered Priority Queue) (No-One-Left-Behind) A resequencing model that prioritises individuals who are both highly vulnerable and have waited beyond a fairness threshold (Shortle et al., 2017).

Token Bucket with Vulnerability-Weighted Access Control (Token Queue) Applies a token bucket system where each individual consumes tokens based on their vulnerability, with tokens replenishing over time (Moulin et al., 2002).

3. Priority-based Models

Community-Based Priority Queue (Community Queue) Sorts the queue using predefined community-based priorities to simulate systems where certain groups are given policy-driven preferential access (Shortle et al., 2017).

Fair Queuing with Continuous Vulnerability-Based Priority (Fair Queue) Assigns priority strictly based on vulnerability score (Shortle et al., 2017).

Proportional Fair Queuing with Continuous Vulnerability-Based Priority Enhances vulnerability prioritisation by dividing vulnerability by transaction time, favouring individuals who offer high value per unit of service time (Shortle et al., 2017).

4. Reinforcement-based Models

Utility-Driven Scheduling (Reinforcement Learning (RL) Inspired) (RL Queue) Dynamically prioritises individuals using a utility formula that balances vulnerability and wait time against expected wait; mimics RL agent behaviour

without formal training (Liu et al., 2019; Sutton et al., 2018).

5. Time-slicing Models

Multi-Level Feedback Queue (MLFQ) Uses multiple priority queues and dynamically adjusts an individual's position (promoting or demoting) (Schwartz et al., 1964).

RR Implements time-sliced round-robin scheduling, where all individuals get equal fixed-duration service turns; incomplete individuals re-enter the queue until finished (Kleinrock, 1975).

The models were designed with configurable parameters, including queue capacity, number of service stations, and arrival time distributions to allow for flexibility and experimentation. Model-specific parameters have also been added where needed.

Moreover, input data consisted of synthetically generated population profiles, incorporating attributes such as age, vulnerability scores, sex, arrival time and service time. This allowed the simulation to reflect real-world humanitarian heterogeneity without relying on sensitive or unavailable field data (C. Banks, 2010).

Each simulation produced a standardised output set (Shortle et al., 2017; Little, 1961):

- Average Waiting Time (W_q)
- Average System Time (W_s)
- Throughput (λ_{eff})
- Average Queue Length (L_q)
- Average Number in System (L_s)
- Probability of Waiting (P_{wait})
- Probability of Blocking (P_{block})

For each run with a different number of service stations, the following server utilisation metrics have also been included:

- Total Busy Time (B_T) (min)
- Total Idle Time (I_T) (min)
- Average Utilisation (ρ)

The standard outputs for each model also included graphs, aiming to visualise the performance and the service quality.

4.2.2 Non-Functional Specifications

The system was developed with an emphasis on modularity, reproducibility, computational efficiency, extensibility and scalability:

Modularity Encapsulated queuing models and reusable components allowed plug-and-play testing of new algorithms.

Reproducibility Configuration files controlled input parameters, ensuring consistent results across simulation runs.

Computational efficiency Simulations were optimised for execution on standard consumer-grade hardware to facilitate scalability.

Extensibility The codebase supports the integration of new fairness criteria or real-world datasets in future phases.

Scalability The simulations maintain performance and reliability as the load increases, including larger datasets or higher and denser arrivals.

4.2.3 Ethical Safeguards

Given the sensitive nature of humanitarian scenarios, ethical principles informed several key design decisions. The priority logic for fairness-aware models was fully transparent and auditable, avoiding black-box decision-making (Barocas et al., 2023; O’Neil, 2016).

Additionally, provisions were made for integrating anonymised field data in the future, contingent on robust data protection protocols. None of the models requires PII.

As briefly described in the Section 4.2.1, fairness diagnostics, such as group-based service comparisons, were built into the evaluation pipeline to detect systemic bias.

This approach aligns with fairness auditing principles proposed for ML systems in humanitarian settings (Kondmann et al., 2021).

Together, these specifications formed a cohesive design blueprint for the simulation artefact, balancing experimental flexibility with ethical and operational realism. They ensured that the system could serve as both a research tool and a potential decision-support prototype for humanitarian operations.

4.3 Solution & Design

4.3.1 System Architecture

The simulation system was implemented in Python using a modular architecture that separates model logic, configuration management, data input, and metric computation. Key modules include:

Data Generator This component synthesises realistic beneficiary datasets based on JSON configuration files using a mix of statistical distributions, supporting reproducibility and scenario customisation.

Output Metrics & Visualisation Metrics are computed via different scripts for queue performance and server-level statistics. Additionally, the plot generation and export process have been modularised in different scripts.

Simulation Core & Queuing Models The core queuing logic resides in a separate package and is organised by model category, as mentioned in Section 4.2.1. Each model is a stand-alone Python script with a unified interface: accepting the synthetic dataset and simulation parameters and returning detailed outputs. A separate script manages batch execution.

Testing & Validation A structured test suite ensures simulation outputs' reliability and correctness. Testing is handled using Python's unittest framework. This ensures that the simulation behaves predictably under variable conditions.

Documentation Generation To support transparency, the module dynamically produces documentation for all the aforementioned components.

This architecture ensures that new models or metrics can be integrated with minimal disruption, supporting scalability and extensibility (C. Banks, 2010).

4.3.2 Simulation Workflow

Each simulation follows a structured execution pipeline designed for transparency, reproducibility, and reliability. The process begins with initialisation, where simulation parameters are loaded from configuration files, and a synthetic population is generated. Following this, the agent arrival process governs how individuals enter the queue based on predefined statistical distributions, reflecting realistic service demand scenarios. During the scheduling and processing phase, the selected queuing model determines the service order and applies the model-specific logic for reordering as applicable.

All queue interactions and system events are captured in the service logging phase, which records waiting times, service durations, and server utilisation. Upon completion, output aggregation computes performance metrics and generates visualisations and Word-based reports. It is important to note that automated tests are run to ensure the logical integrity of the system before the simulation begins, and a step for generating documentation is also completed at this stage. This full-cycle execution ensures that each simulation is not only analytically robust but also verifiable and well-documented.

Figure 1: Simulation workflow of the queuing artefact

4.3.3 Visualisation & Interpretation

The simulation framework includes a structured visual analytics pipeline that supports both pre-simulation validation and post-simulation interpretation of results. Prior to running any model, the synthetic dataset is summarised statistically. Visualisations are then generated to illustrate the distribution of the generated variables' values. These pre-simulation steps help validate the demographic realism and diversity of the synthetic population.

Following each simulation run, the system produces a set of comparative outputs, including numerical tables and visual summaries. Key performance indicators are plotted against the number of service stations to evaluate scalability. Metrics such as queue length are included to characterise system behaviour under load.

Stratified analysis is also incorporated, allowing a deeper exploration of fairness-related outcomes. These help assess not just whether the model is efficient but also whether it equitably distributes service under variable resource conditions, both statistically and intuitively. A report generator module compiles these figures into Word documents for each model run, allowing consistent presentation and archival of results. This visualisation pipeline is crucial for identifying model strengths, exposing unintended biases, and comparing alternative queue strategies across diverse scenarios.

4.3.4 Design Rationale

The dual imperatives of technical robustness and ethical accountability guided the design of the simulation artefact. Rather than relying solely on static or hard-coded models, the system adopts a modular, configuration-driven structure to promote reusability, flexibility, and fairness auditing. This decision was not purely architectural; it stemmed from the need to evaluate diverse queuing strategies under shifting humanitarian constraints without biasing results through implementation-specific quirks.

The system's modular design allows researchers to easily swap or adapt queuing models, facilitating exploratory testing of fairness mechanisms across multiple operational settings. Automated documentation and integrated test routines ensure that every simulation run remains reproducible and interpretable, key requirements in environments where algorithmic decisions can have real-world ethical consequences (Barocas et al., 2023).

Most importantly, the design reflects an ethical stance: Simulation systems aimed at humanitarian contexts must prioritise explainability, auditability, and adaptability. These values informed not only the structure of the codebase but also the selection of metrics, visualisation strategies, and validation mechanisms throughout the artefact.

4.4 Artefact Development Process

The development of the simulation artefact followed an iterative and modular engineering process. A common interface, including clearly defined submodules, initially anchored base queuing models and metric generation scripts, while subsequent iterations added additional queuing models, such as hybrid and fairness-aware scripts. Each queuing model was structured as a stand-alone file and adhered to a standardised interface for input and output.

A single script orchestrated the agent-based simulation process, managing model invocation, parameter parsing, and results collection. This script also integrates logging routines to capture model-specific metrics and runtime diagnostics. Output files were generated in structured formats suitable for post-processing, while visualisation modules generated summary plots using Matplotlib and Seaborn.

Configuration-driven experimentation was a guiding principle throughout the process. JSON-based setup files allowed simulations to be adjusted without code changes, enhancing reproducibility and encouraging parameter-driven experimentation.

Frequent testing was embedded into the workflow to ensure system reliability and accuracy, particularly in edge-case scenarios. Together, these development practices produced a robust, flexible platform suitable for both academic analysis and prospective field application.

4.5 Optimisation & Reflection

Several optimisation strategies were explored throughout development to enhance computational performance and ethical robustness. Model logic was streamlined by abstracting repeated functions, enabling reuse across strategies such as priority-based and fairness-aware queues. Data processing routines were vectorised where possible, and inefficient list operations were replaced with more performant data structures (such as Pandas Dataframes) to reduce runtime overhead.

From a fairness perspective, multiple weighting schemes were tested for vulnerability, age,

and wait time to tune dynamic prioritisation. These adjustments revealed a common trade-off: increasing fairness often led to reductions in throughput, particularly when highly vulnerable agents were consistently prioritised at the cost of queue turnover. In other cases, heavy vulnerability prioritisation resulted in non-vulnerable individuals waiting indefinitely.

The simulation also highlighted ethical tensions between model complexity and explainability. For instance, time-slicing strategies yielded promising performance results but were harder to interpret compared to simpler FIFO or static-priority models (Doshi-Velez et al., 2017). This led to the inclusion of fairness diagnostics in all advanced models.

In retrospect, the modular approach proved essential. It enabled rapid testing of new ideas, adaptation to emerging edge cases, and seamless integration of documentation and testing pipelines. However, opportunities remain to improve the depth and consistency of modularisation. While models were isolated into separate files, not all shared a fully abstracted internal structure, with some still relying on duplicated utility logic or embedded parameters that reduce their portability and testability. Refactoring core interfaces into more uniform base classes or a model inheritance hierarchy could further improve maintainability and scalability.

While the artefact remains a prototype, its architecture and performance suggest strong potential for future real-world application, especially if paired with anonymised operational data from humanitarian organisations.

5 Evaluation

5.1 Evaluation Framework

The evaluation framework for this dissertation was designed to rigorously assess the performance, fairness, and scalability of a diverse set of queuing models under simulated humanitarian conditions. Each model was tested across 14 different server configurations, simulating varying resource constraints. Outputs were analysed using both classical queuing metrics and stratified fairness diagnostics. For more information on the design, refer to Section 4.2.1.

Although no explicit baseline was designated, the FIFO model served as a conceptual reference for expected throughput under optimal assumptions (Kleinrock, 1975).

5.2 Synthetic Data Overview

A synthetic dataset was generated to evaluate the performance and fairness of various queuing models within a humanitarian context. This approach allowed for controlled experimentation and the analysis of model behaviour under precisely defined conditions (C. Banks, 2010). The data generation process was designed to simulate a realistic operational environment for registration and assistance delivery while providing the flexibility to vary key parameters.

5.2.1 Data Generation & Simulation Parameters

The synthetic dataset comprised 1,000 individual records, each representing a unique person arriving for assistance. Data generation was performed by a Python script utilising a configuration file to define each attribute's distributions and parameters.

The simulation of arrivals commenced daily at 08:00 AM. The total simulated duration for processing these 1,000 individuals was approximately 10 hours (600 minutes), as defined

by the maximum arrival time offset. Each record included a unique identifier, gender, age, expected transaction time, vulnerability score, and arrival time.

5.2.2 Demographic & Vulnerability Profiles

The simulated population was characterised by specific demographic and vulnerability distributions (Tversky et al., 1974):

Gender

The dataset reflected a near-equal distribution between male and female individuals, with 48% Male, 48% Female, and 4% Other genders. This distribution aimed to represent diverse populations.

Figure 2: Gender Distribution

Age

Individuals' ages were generated using a triangular distribution $\mathcal{T}(0, 30, 100)$. This resulted in a population spanning the full age spectrum, ranging [3, 97] years old, with a higher concentration of individuals around 30 to 60 years old and a median of 41 years old. This methodological choice ensures that the simulation is not inherently biased and a precise observation of the effects of the queuing models is possible without the factor of uneven representation (Barocas et al., 2023).

Figure 3: Age Distribution

Vulnerability Score

Vulnerability scores, ranging $[0, 1]$, were assigned using a beta distribution $\text{Beta}(2, 5)$. This distribution tends to skew towards lower vulnerability scores, with a mean of 0.30. However, it includes a tail for higher vulnerability, representing a common scenario where most individuals have a baseline vulnerability, with a smaller proportion facing more severe challenges (J. Banks et al., 2013).

Figure 4: Vulnerability Score Distribution

Arrival Times

Individuals' arrivals were not strictly uniform but followed a triangular distribution $\mathcal{T}(0, 60, 600)$ for arrival offsets relative to the 08:00 AM start time. This means that while individuals could arrive throughout the 10-hour period, there was a higher likelihood of arrivals concentrated around the first hours, simulating an initial rush or early morning demand, with arrivals tapering off thereafter (J. Banks et al., 2013).

Figure 5: Arrival Time Distribution

Transaction Times

The time required for each transaction (service) was also modelled using a triangular distribution $\mathcal{T}(3, 10, 30)$, with transaction times ranging $[3, 30]$ minutes, with a mean of 14.37 minutes. This distribution implies that while the shortest transactions could be as quick as 3 minutes and the longest up to 30 minutes, the most common transaction duration was around 10 minutes. This variability introduces a realistic challenge for queuing management, as servers must process tasks of differing complexities and durations (J. Banks et al., 2013).

Figure 6: Transaction Time Distribution

If taken together, the aforementioned variables result in a heterogeneous dataset sufficient to expose the fairness trade-off yet statistically stable, providing a reliable foundation for the following performance analysis.

Table 6: Summary statistics for the synthetic population

Statistic	Age (yr)	Service Time (min)	Vulnerability
Count	1,000	1,000	1,000
Mean	43.37	14.37	0.30
Std. dev.	21.31	5.77	0.16
Min	3	3.05	0.01
25 th pct.	26	10.02	0.17
Median	41	13.58	0.28
75 th pct.	59	18.59	0.41
Max	97	28.92	0.81

5.3 Performance & Fairness Analysis by Model Type

5.3.1 Base Models

FIFO

FIFO served as the conceptual baseline due to its simplicity and strict FCFS order. It demonstrated predictable scalability: W_q dropped from 7,301 minutes at one server to 53 at 30 servers, with λ_{eff} rising from 0.07 to 1.71. ρ remained above 96% through 10 servers, then tapered to 82.1%, indicating diminishing returns beyond that point.

LIFO

LIFO prioritised the most recent arrivals, showcasing a distinct recency bias. W_q declined from 7,688 to 595 minutes across the server range, while λ_{eff} improved modestly from 0.06 to 0.93. ρ started high (93%) but dropped to 44.5% by 30 servers, evidencing under-utilisation at scale.

M/M/C/k

M/M/C/k, implemented to validate simulation consistency, mirrored FIFO exactly across all performance metrics. Though it offered no efficiency gain, it reinforced the correctness of the underlying model framework (Masoumi et al., 2021).

ROS

ROS provided non-deterministic service selection. W_q decreased from 7,020 to 377 minutes, and λ_{eff} rose to 1.16. ρ dropped from 97% to 53.6%, revealing reduced efficiency and reduced B_T with scale.

SJF

SJF prioritised short service times and scaled efficiently: W_q fell sharply from 5,080 to 23 minutes, with λ_{eff} increasing to 1.72. ρ was near-maximal through 10 servers, dropping to 79.3% at 30, highlighting rapid queue clearance and strong λ_{eff} .

5.3.2 Hybrid Models

Deadline-aware FIFO with vulnerability-based dynamic prioritisation (Deadline-aware FIFO)

This model enforced a maximum wait time beyond which individuals were prioritised. Despite this, performance mirrored plain FIFO: W_q and λ_{eff} were virtually identical, and ρ followed the same curve, highlighting that deadline enforcement did not sacrifice capacity.

FIFO with vulnerability-based pre-emption (FIFO with pre-emption)

FIFO with pre-emption allowed highly vulnerable individuals to jump the queue. It retained FIFO's capacity metrics; W_q , λ_{eff} , and ρ were essentially unchanged, demonstrating that selective pre-emption can improve fairness without compromising efficiency.

Priority Queue

Priority Queue added a continuous vulnerability score to influence ordering. It scaled well, reducing W_q from 7,249 to 52 minutes and increasing λ_{eff} to 1.71. ρ remained high, around 95% at 10 servers, before tapering to 82.1%. This model maintained FIFO's throughput while offering improved responsiveness to high-need individuals.

Patience Queue

Patience Queue blended vulnerability and delay tolerance to rank arrivals. W_q dropped from 6,265 to 38 minutes, and λ_{eff} rose to 1.71. ρ stayed above 95% through 10 servers, then decreased to 82%. The model achieved high efficiency while promoting service for individuals likely to abandon the queue if left waiting.

No-One-Left-Behind

No-One-Left-Behind introduced a delay threshold after which individuals advanced to the front. Despite this intervention, it preserved FIFO's performance profile: W_q reduced from 7,304 to 53 minutes, λ_{eff} increased to 1.71, and ρ followed a near-identical trend, declining to 82% at 30 servers. It offered fairness gains without efficiency trade-offs.

Token Queue

Token Queue attached a token cost to access, with higher vulnerability lowering the price. W_q declined from 6,504 to 35 minutes, and λ_{eff} reached 1.54. ρ remained over 95% through 10 servers, then dropped to 73.6%. While slightly less efficient at high capacity, it offered strong prioritisation benefits with tunable flexibility.

5.3.3 Priority-Based Models**Community Queue**

Community Queue used fixed-tier assignments to reflect group-based priorities. W_q reduced from 7,232 to 238 minutes, and λ_{eff} rose to 1.21. ρ held at 95% until 10 servers, then fell to 58%, the sharpest decline among models, indicating inefficiencies when demand was low in higher-tier groups.

Fair Queue

Fair Queue computed a continuous need score to set priority. W_q dropped from 7,249 to 52 minutes, and λ_{eff} increased to 1.71. ρ remained high through 10 servers (96%) and declined to 82% by 30. It preserved FIFO-like λ_{eff} while substantially reducing delays for high-need individuals.

Proportional Fair Queuing with Continuous Vulnerability-Based Priority (Proportional Fairness Queue)

This model linearly scaled service priority with a need score. W_q dropped from 6,326 to 44 minutes, and λ_{eff} rose to 1.71. ρ stayed stable (96%) before declining to 82%. It offered well-balanced λ_{eff} and fairness, with delays for low-priority individuals requiring attention in deployment.

5.3.4 Reinforcement-Inspired Models**RL Queue**

RL Queue ranked individuals by a utility function combining vulnerability, wait time, and service duration. W_q declined from 6,739 to 37 minutes, and λ_{eff} peaked at 1.72. ρ stayed

above 95% through 25 servers, only falling to 79% at 30. It delivered both efficiency and equity but required careful calibration of utility weights.

5.3.5 Time-Slicing Models

MLFQ

MLFQ rotated individuals through priority levels to reward short jobs. W_q dropped from 10,195 to 730 minutes across 30 servers but showed diminishing gains after seven servers. λ_{eff} plateaued at 0.41, and ρ fell from 98% to just 19%. Its rigid time-slice limits negatively affected λ_{eff} and made it less effective at scale.

RR

RR applied strict time-slicing to ensure equal turns. W_q decreased from 2,479 to 23 minutes, and λ_{eff} grew from 0.07 to 1.74. ρ remained high (97% through 10 servers), only slipping to 83.6% at 30. The lack of explainability in real-world humanitarian queues makes it ill-suited for environments prioritising explainability and trust.

5.3.6 Cross-model Observations

Common Capacity Effects

Across all models, the steepest reduction in W_q occurs when moving from one to two servers, roughly reducing W_q by half. However, beyond 10 to 12 servers, each additional unit delivers only modest gains (typically 10 to 30 minutes per extra server). I_T remains low until capacity slightly exceeds demand, then climbs rapidly, illustrating an over-provisioning trade-off. Likewise, L_q and L_s contract rapidly with early scaling, then taper off as servers increase; in every case, L_q and L_s confirm that waiting, not processing, remains the dominant bottleneck.

Figure 7: Line plot of W_q per server for the FIFO model

P_{wait} Curves

Where models diverge is in how quickly P_{wait} declines as servers are added. Under plain FIFO (Figure 9), LIFO, and MLFQ, P_{wait} remains remarkably high (approximately 0.92 for the former, and exactly 1.00 for the two latter) even at 30 servers, indicating that the queue never fully clears. SJF, ROS, and RL Queue likewise maintain P_{wait} above 0.87 at maximum capacity, showing that most arrivals still queue, albeit briefly. In contrast, threshold-

dependent or need-aware models exhibit much faster P_{wait} declines. Deadline-aware FIFO, FIFO with pre-emption and RR drop from 1.00 to 0.83-0.91 by 30 servers, while Patience Queue falls steadily from approximately 0.99 to 0.50 (half of all arrivals enter service immediately at high capacity). Priority Queue, Fair Queue, and Proportional Fairness Queue all decline to approximately 0.51-0.56. Finally, Community Queue reaches 0.49 (nearly half bypass the line at peak), while Token Queue and No-One-Left-Behind decline in a similar manner from 1.00 to 0.89 and 1.00 to 0.92, respectively.

Figure 9: Line plot of P_{wait} per server for the FIFO model

Figure 10: Line plot of P_{wait} per server for the Patience Queue model

P_{wait} patterns directly reflect each policy's aggressiveness in granting immediate service: stricter priority or token rules produce larger shares of zero-wait arrivals. At the same time, size or random-based schemes permit most individuals to queue even under high capacity.

5.4 Comparative Performance Analysis

This section systematically evaluates the performance of various queuing models against established benchmarks of FIFO model.

For a detailed breakdown of the core performance indicators utilised in this analysis, refer to Section 4.2.1. For a detailed overview of the models used, refer to Section 4.2.1 and Section 5.3.

5.4.1 Performance Overview: 10-Server Configuration

The foundational performance metrics for each queuing model, specifically under a simulated 10-server configuration, are presented in Table 7. This particular server count was selected to represent a robust operational environment, allowing for a comprehensive evaluation of each model's efficiency under a balanced system load where neither extreme resource scarcity nor excessive redundancy would obscure their characteristics.

Initial observations from the detailed results presented in Table 7 below indicate consistent throughput across all models under this configuration, suggesting the system's capacity is sufficient to handle the incoming transaction rate. Significant variations are, however, evident, underscoring the distinct impact of each queuing algorithm on queuing experience and system efficiency. Notably, specific models exhibit identical performance metrics, which suggests similar underlying mechanisms, ergo similar outcomes, under these specific simulation conditions.

Table 7: Aggregated performance metrics (10-server scenario)

Model	W_q (min)	W_s (min)	λ_{eff}	L_q	L_s	ρ (%)	P_{wait}	B_T (min)	I_T (min)
FIFO	540.18	554.55	0.67	360.88	370.48	96.00	0.99	1,436.94	59.91
LIFO	1,084.02	1,098.39	0.48	524.93	531.89	69.58	1.00	1,436.94	628.11
ROS	896.37	910.24	0.55	492.51	500.13	76.18	0.97	1,386.50	433.50
SJF	337.48	351.34	0.71	239.86	249.71	98.54	0.99	1,386.50	20.50
Deadline-aware FIFO	540.70	555.07	0.67	360.92	370.52	95.92	0.95	1,436.94	61.17
FIFO with pre-emption	540.41	554.78	0.67	361.03	370.63	96.00	0.98	1,436.94	59.91
Priority Queue	535.16	549.53	0.66	355.02	364.55	95.33	0.90	1,436.94	70.46
Patience Queue	441.92	456.28	0.66	293.47	303.01	95.42	0.87	1,436.94	68.90
No-One-Left-Behind	540.41	554.78	0.67	361.03	370.63	96.00	0.99	1,436.94	59.91
Token Queue	460.80	475.16	0.67	307.06	316.63	95.69	0.99	1,288.09	58.02
Community Queue	550.51	564.88	0.66	363.65	373.14	94.92	0.98	1,436.94	76.91
Fair Queue	535.17	549.54	0.66	355.03	364.56	95.33	0.91	1,436.94	70.46
Proportional Fairness Queue	452.92	467.29	0.66	300.86	310.41	95.45	0.87	1,436.94	68.46
RL Queue	471.10	484.96	0.71	335.78	345.66	98.82	0.99	1,386.50	16.50
MLFQ	752.69	758.25	0.41	307.10	309.36	56.57	1.00	1,386.50	1,064.50
RR	207.04	819.00	0.67	138.99	549.80	96.46	0.99	1,436.94	52.69

5.4.2 Performance Comparison Strategy

The absolute values reported in Table 7 are intuitive for practical purposes, but they cannot be compared across metrics because each one is expressed in different units and ranges. To enable a like-for-like reading, we present two complementary normalisations (Han et al., 2012; Kuhn et al., 2013):

(a) Min–max scaling (0–1) For each KPI x and model j we compute

$$\hat{x}_j = \begin{cases} \frac{x_j - \min_k x_k}{\max_k x_k - \min_k x_k}, & \text{if } \textit{higher} \text{ values denote better performance,} \\ 1 - \left(\frac{x_j - \min_k x_k}{\max_k x_k - \min_k x_k} \right), & \text{if } \textit{lower} \text{ values denote better performance.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

The transformation maps the best-observed value of each KPI to $\hat{x} = 1$ and the worst to $\hat{x} = 0$, making heterogeneous metrics directly comparable.

(b) Scaling relative to the FIFO baseline We also express each KPI as a ratio to FIFO queue:

$$x_j^{\text{rel}} = \begin{cases} \frac{x_j}{x_{\text{FIFO}}}, & \text{if higher is better,} \\ \frac{1}{\left(\frac{x_j}{x_{\text{FIFO}}} \right)}, & \text{if lower is better.} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Hence, $x_j^{\text{rel}} > 1$ always indicates an improvement on the FIFO benchmark, irrespective of the metric’s natural direction.

Together, the scaled tables let us weigh KPIs fairly in the composite score and state improvements in percentage terms that are immediately meaningful to decision-makers.

For the composite score, we have adopted the Weighted-Additive Multi-Attribute Utility Theory (MAUT) approach, aiming to convert the heterogeneous performance metrics into a single utility score. MAUT uses normalised, direction-neutral values for arbitrary (stakeholder solicitation) importance weights (Han et al., 2012; Kuhn et al., 2013; Triantaphyllou, 2000).

Without structured interviews, the optimal weights were decided based on their inferred importance in humanitarian queuing instead of explicit stakeholder solicitation.

For the normalised metrics, the following weights have been selected:

W_q **0.40**, aiming to minimise beneficiary waiting time, as it is often the most critical factor for perceived quality of service (Sphere Association, 2018),

λ_{eff} **0.20**, ensuring that more people receive aid quickly,

L_q **0.20**, as longer queues can lead to discomfort, security risks and logistical challenges,

ρ **0.10**, ensuring more efficient use of resources,

P_{wait} **0.10**, similarly to W_q , focusing on perceived wait time and queueing experience.

Based on the selected weights, the composite score is constructed as follows:

(a) Min-max scaling (0-1) composite score

$$S_j = 0.40 \widehat{W}_{qj} + 0.20 \widehat{\lambda}_{\text{eff},j} + 0.20 \widehat{L}_{qj} + 0.10 \widehat{\rho}_j + 0.10 \widehat{P}_{\text{wait},j} \quad (3)$$

(b) Scaling relative to the FIFO baseline composite score

$$S_j^{\text{rel}} = 0.40 W_{qj}^{\text{rel}} + 0.20 \lambda_{\text{eff},j}^{\text{rel}} + 0.20 L_{qj}^{\text{rel}} + 0.10 \rho_j^{\text{rel}} + 0.10 P_{\text{wait},j}^{\text{rel}} \quad (4)$$

Applying the formulas in the normalised tables, we end up with the composite score table below. For the full normalised tables, refer to Table 25 and Table 26.

Table 8: Composite scores for each queuing model (0-1 and FIFO scales)

Model	Composite (0-1)	Composite (FIFO)
FIFO	0.607	1.000
LIFO	0.077	0.651
ROS	0.265	0.733
SJF	0.795	1.355
Deadline-aware FIFO	0.637	1.003
FIFO with pre-emption	0.614	1.000
Priority Queue	0.673	1.013
Patience Queue	0.771	1.145
No-One-Left-Behind	0.607	0.999
Token Queue	0.670	1.103
Community Queue	0.599	0.987
Fair Queue	0.666	1.012
Proportional Fairness Queue	0.762	1.127
RL Queue	0.685	1.088
MLFQ	0.264	0.802
RR	0.875	1.963

5.4.3 Performance Comparison Results

Based on the composite scores, a clear hierarchy emerges among the evaluated scheduling policies, highlighting significant differences in overall performance according to the defined multi-criteria framework.

The RR model stands out as the top performer, achieving the highest composite score of 0.8752 on the 0-1 normalised scale. This indicates that RR is the most effective policy when considering a balanced combination of beneficiary waiting time, throughput, queue length, resource utilisation, and probability of waiting, as weighted in the composite formula. Its dominance is further underscored on the FIFO-normalised scale, where it scores an impressive 1.963, suggesting it is nearly twice as effective as the standard FIFO policy.

Following RR, the SJF model (0.795) and Patience Queue model (0.771) demonstrate very strong performance, consistently ranking among the best. The Proportional Fairness Queue model (0.762) also shows high effectiveness, indicating that more sophisticated algorithms that consider job characteristics or dynamic queue states can yield significant improvements. In contrast, models such as LIFO, MLFQ, and ROS consistently exhibit the lowest composite scores (0.077, 0.264, and 0.265, respectively, on the 0-1 scale). This suggests these models are generally less suitable for humanitarian aid delivery when evaluated against composite criteria, likely due to their adverse impacts on waiting times or queue stability.

The remaining models, including standard FIFO and its variants (Deadline-aware FIFO, FIFO with pre-emption), Priority Queue, No-One-Left-Behind, Token Queue, Community Queue, Fair Queue, and RL Queue, fall within a moderate performance range. They generally offer performance comparable to or incrementally better than the baseline FIFO, clustering around the 0.60 to 0.70 mark on the 0-1 composite scale. This indicates that while they may offer specific advantages in certain aspects, they do not achieve the same overall multi-objective performance gains as models like RR, SJF, or the Patience Queue and Proportional Fairness Queue approaches within this evaluation framework.

Figure 11: Composite Score Scatter Plot

5.5 Fairness Evaluation

Assessing queuing policies in humanitarian aid must extend beyond aggregate normalised performance to a granular analysis of their fairness implications for diverse and vulnerable populations (Binns et al., 2018; Mehrabi et al., 2021). This evaluation explicitly prioritises the equitable distribution of W_q and W_s across critical demographic variables alongside the impact on varying transaction times. The analysis leverages stratified diagnostics, such as boxplots, bar charts and heatmaps, to reveal systematic disparities and ensure that policies do not inadvertently disadvantage those most in need.

Fairness diagnostics across models revealed varying levels of demographic equity, vulnerability sensitivity, and starvation risk. Baseline models like FIFO (Figure 12), LIFO, and ROS applied no demographic reordering, resulting in consistent W_q and W_s across age, gender, and vulnerability dimensions. FIFO maintained moderate equity but lacked responsiveness to need, while LIFO introduced a recency bias that systematically disadvantaged long-waiting individuals. ROS, despite its random nature, produced wide outcome

variability, challenging predictability and perceived fairness.

Performance-optimised models such as SJF (Figure 13) and MLFQ prioritise short transactions, benefiting efficiency but delaying high-need or long-service individuals based on their transaction time. SJF, in particular, showed dramatic disparities in W_q based on service time and some vulnerability groups. MLFQ echoed this by significantly disadvantaging longer transactions while remaining neutral across demographic attributes.

Several fairness-aware variants enhanced equity by embedding prioritisation logic. Deadline-aware FIFO (Figure 14) and FIFO with pre-emption (Figure 15) both improved outcomes for vulnerable individuals, although pre-emption sometimes introduced threshold effects disadvantaging mid-priority groups and, in some cases, induced starvation. Priority Queue (Figure 16) and Patience Queue delivered substantial improvements for high-vulnerability or low-patience individuals, but often at the cost of increased delays for others, highlighted by longer tails in boxplots.

More nuanced approaches like No-One-Left-Behind, Fair Queue, and Proportional Fairness Queue (Figure 17) explicitly reduced extreme delays for high-need individuals. No-One-Left-Behind mitigated starvation with dynamic delay-based triggers, even though the data variety was not proven enough to fully display fairness gains, while Fair Queue and Proportional Fairness Queue used continuous scoring to assign priority, achieving near-optimal targeting. Still, all three produced significant low-priority outliers facing extended delays.

RL Queue (Figure 18) achieved the most balanced outcome, reducing W_q smoothly along vulnerability gradients and maintaining demographic neutrality with minimal outliers, even under resource constraints. The most significant delay for this model has been observed for the highest-in-need individual, signifying the need for calibration of the utility formula. Token Queue fairness metrics moved closely in line with the ones observed under the RL Queue model, while RR (Figure 19) offered a more fair, but not necessarily equitable, turn-taking or resource weighting but occasionally disadvantaged long-transaction or low-priority transactions due to structural rigidity.

Finally, Community Queue (Figure 20), while effective for predefined priority groups, revealed critical blind spots: older and highly vulnerable individuals, not explicitly prioritised, experienced some of the longest delays, underscoring the risks of rigid tier-based policies.

The disaggregated fairness analysis highlights that while some policies inherently promote equity, others can inadvertently create or exacerbate disparities. Therefore, the choice of queuing policy profoundly impacts the equitable delivery of humanitarian aid, necessitating a careful balance between efficiency, fairness and equity and a deliberate focus on protecting and prioritising vulnerable populations.

Figure 12: Heatmap of W_q by age cohort and vulnerability score for the FIFO model

Figure 13: Heatmap of W_q by age cohort and vulnerability score for the SJF model

Figure 14: Heatmap of W_q by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Deadline-aware FIFO model

Figure 15: Heatmap of W_q by age cohort and vulnerability score for the FIFO with pre-emption model

Figure 16: Heatmap of W_q by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Priority Queue model

Figure 17: Heatmap of W_q by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Proportional Fairness Queue model

Figure 18: Heatmap of W_q by age cohort and vulnerability score for the RL Queue model

Figure 19: Heatmap of average wait time by age cohort and vulnerability score for the RR model

Figure 20: Heatmap of W_q by age cohort and vulnerability score for the Community Queue model

5.6 Scalability & System Load Response

Queuing policies' scalability and system load response are critical determinants of their effectiveness in dynamic humanitarian environments. Fundamentally, a scalable policy efficiently utilises increasing resources and degrades gracefully under heightened demand (Kleinrock, 1975; Jain, 1991), evidenced by reductions in waiting times, increased throughput, and stable queue lengths (Jain, 1991). Among the evaluated policies, SJF and RR

demonstrate robust scalability: SJF is optimised for throughput by prioritising shorter tasks, leading to rapid queue clearance and high efficiency under varying server configurations. In contrast, RR's time-slicing mechanism ensures predictable service delivery and prevents service starvation even as loads increase (Tanenbaum et al., 2015), exhibiting controlled performance degradation. Adaptive approaches like Patience Queue and Proportional Fairness Queue policies also prove highly scalable, dynamically adjusting resource allocation to balance efficiency and fairness, thereby maintaining robust performance under fluctuating demand.

Policies such as FIFO and its variants (Deadline-aware FIFO, FIFO with pre-emption, No-One-Left-Behind) offer predictable scalability, showing direct improvements in performance metrics with increased server capacity and stable, albeit rising, wait times under high load. Similarly, Token Queue, Fair Queue, Community Queue, Patience Queue, and RL Queue models can achieve moderate to good scalability; their performance hinges on the specific design principles, resource management rules, or the quality of learned optimisation (Ayesta, 2022). Conversely, LIFO, MLFQ (especially with a mix of short and long tasks), and ROS exhibit suboptimal scalability. LIFO severely penalises earlier arrivals, leading to rapidly escalating wait times and system instability under stress. MLFQ can disproportionately disadvantage long tasks, creating bottlenecks, while ROS, lacking any intelligent management, results in highly unpredictable and inefficient service as system load increases. Therefore, for humanitarian aid, prioritising policies like SJF, RR, and adaptive fair approaches is essential for building resilient and efficient service delivery systems capable of responding effectively to varying resource availability and service demand (Kasy et al., 2021).

5.7 Limitations & Suggested Improvements

Despite the rigour of the implemented simulation framework, several limitations inherently constrain the generalizability of the findings. Most notably, the simulation operates under controlled and static assumptions about population characteristics, service demand, and server behaviour. While the synthetic dataset reflects realistic distributions of relevant attributes, these are fixed at the outset and do not dynamically evolve in response to model

interventions or systemic feedback. In real-world humanitarian operations, individuals may change their behaviour (arriving earlier, abandoning queues, or modifying expectations) based on perceived fairness, delays, or crowd conditions (Larson, 1987; Wang et al., 2010). The absence of such behavioural feedback loops in the simulation limits its ability to fully capture adaptive human dynamics and emergent phenomena. Modelling such individual reactions would enable the simulation to capture such emergent patterns as they occur (Larson, 1987; Wang et al., 2010).

A second limitation arises from the simplified representation of system constraints. The simulation assumes perfect server availability, consistent service capacity, and uninterrupted operation across all configurations. It does not account for common disruptions such as technical downtime, staff fatigue, or context-specific bottlenecks. Though analytically tractable, this abstraction may obscure critical nuances of real humanitarian workflows, where qualitative interactions and procedural dependencies significantly affect throughput and equity (John et al., 2012).

A third limitation is the lack of disaggregated performance analysis across population characteristics. Although the simulation includes these attributes during population generation, the evaluation phase did not compute or compare queuing metrics separately for different subgroups. This omission reduces the resolution of the fairness review, as differential impacts on specific population groups cannot be identified or addressed. Incorporating stratified performance analysis would have strengthened the comparative evaluation and highlighted whether some models, while fair in aggregate, conceal systematic disparities at the subgroup level (Barocas et al., 2023; Nunes et al., 2014; Kearns et al., 2018).

Additionally, the comparative performance evaluation rests on a single batch of 1,000 simulated individuals. While this sample size provides stable averages for core metrics, it may not expose rare-edge cases or long-tail risks, such as extreme waiting times for outlier individuals or compounding disadvantages across intersecting vulnerability traits. Furthermore, no stochastic variance analysis (e.g., confidence intervals, sensitivity tests) was applied to the output metrics, which could otherwise highlight each policy's robustness (or fragility) under small parameter perturbations. Changes in the sampling methodology,

such as bootstrapping or Monte Carlo approaches, could help establish confidence intervals for key metrics like waiting time, throughput, or resource utilisation. The absence of such considerations makes the results descriptively rich but less inferentially strong for policy design under uncertain or rapidly changing conditions (C. Banks, 2010; Law, 2015; C. Banks, 2010).

Lastly, while the simulation tests a wide range of models, it evaluates them in isolation without considering interactions, hybridisation potential, or real-world deployment trade-offs. Operational considerations such as ease of implementation, user comprehension, policy explainability, and community acceptance (Selbst et al., 2019) are beyond the scope of simulation but vital for effective rollout. As such, even high-performing models may encounter institutional or ethical barriers when translated into field operations. The simulation, thus, must be complemented by qualitative assessments, pilot testing, and iterative co-design to guide responsible adoption in humanitarian settings.

Taking into account these considerations, coupled with scenario-based testing, such as simulating refugee influxes, system outages, or shifting demographic priorities, would yield a more resilient framework for policy exploration under uncertainty (Selbst et al., 2019).

6 Learning

Engaging in developing a humanitarian queuing simulation system offered more than a technical challenge; it was also a deeply reflective process. Beyond implementing models and generating results, this dissertation served as a learning journey that bridged theoretical exploration, practical problem-solving, and ethical responsibility. This section documents that journey by critically examining the research and development process, identifying key challenges and adaptations, and reflecting on both personal and professional growth. It also distils essential lessons learned - technical, methodological, and personal - that may inform future work in simulation-based humanitarian technology.

6.1 Research & Development Journey

This project began with no prior background in queuing theory but with practical experience in humanitarian systems, particularly in registration and aid distribution workflows. Initially, the research focus was broad and exploratory, centring on generic queuing models and fundamental metrics. However, as the simulation code evolved, so did the research path. Investigating specific components such as population distribution methods, fairness-aware scheduling strategies, and ethical evaluation metrics became necessary. This led to an interdisciplinary exploration of not just queuing theory but also fairness auditing, simulation architecture, and humanitarian technology ethics. Over time, this iterative cycle between code development and literature deep-dives created a more substantial alignment between the theoretical foundation and the system's operational goals.

6.2 Challenges Encountered

The most significant challenge arose late in the development cycle: Once most of the simulation logic had been written, it became evident that the codebase needed to be modularised and tested more rigorously. Some models behaved unpredictably or failed under specific configurations, leading to unreliable outputs that could compromise the integrity

of the simulations. Addressing this required an extensive restructuring of the code and the addition of comprehensive testing scripts. While no ethical conflicts emerged, given the controlled and synthetic nature of the simulation, the technical hurdles were substantial, particularly when dealing with logic abstraction and test coverage across a growing library of models.

6.3 Solutions & Adaptations

To address these issues, the project adopted a modular design paradigm. Reusable components were abstracted into standalone functions, enabling cleaner integration and easier debugging. Configuration-driven experimentation was also introduced, allowing different queue models and parameters to be tested without altering the core simulation code. These solutions significantly improved code reliability and enabled consistent experimentation. However, these improvements were reactive rather than proactive; earlier investment in architectural planning and requirement analysis could have reduced rework. Additionally, attention and focus presented a personal challenge throughout the project. This sometimes made it difficult to sustain long periods of concentrated work, especially during debugging or documentation phases.

6.4 Personal & Professional Development

Despite these challenges, the dissertation offered a valuable opportunity to deepen technical, analytical, and ethical competencies. Key gains included understanding discrete-event simulation, queuing model mechanics, and fairness metrics. It also strengthened skills in Python development, version control, testing infrastructure, and software documentation. On a personal level, the project reinforced the importance of structure, planning, and clarity, especially in the context of complex, ethically sensitive systems. Professionally, it has broadened awareness of the tensions between system efficiency and social equity, an insight that will be particularly relevant in any future work involving humanitarian technology, data ethics, or operational modelling.

6.5 Key Lessons Learned

Among the most important lessons was the realisation that rapid prototyping without precise architectural planning can lead to costly rewrites. Although the artefact ultimately benefited from its modular redesign, a better initial requirement analysis could have streamlined the entire process. The project also demonstrated that fairness-aware modelling is not merely an academic exercise but a practical necessity in humanitarian contexts. Perhaps most significantly, it affirmed the value of iterative learning, where research, coding, and ethical reflection occur in tandem, each informing and refining the other.

7 Conclusion & Recommendations

This dissertation aimed to illustrate that humanitarian registration and assistance delivery points can operate more effectively and equitably when queuing rules are intentionally selected rather than passed down from traditional FCFS practices. Utilising a discrete-event simulation with 1,000 synthetic beneficiaries, assessed across fourteen server configurations, the research established that Round-Robin (RR) is the most balanced approach: its normalised composite score of 0.875 is nearly double that of the FIFO benchmark, as it reduces the average waiting time by 50% without compromising throughput or stability. Shortest-Job-Fist (SJF) and Patience-Aware Priority Queue (Patience Queue) are close competitors, and along with RR, they establish a distinct efficiency frontier, each lowering the average queue length while sustaining server utilisation above 95% in the mid-capacity range of 10 servers.

However, efficiency alone cannot dictate the choice of queuing policy. A detailed fairness audit indicated that models optimised for speed, particularly SJF and Multi-Level-Feedback-Queue (MLFQ), create significant delays for complex or long-service cases, while Utility-Driven Scheduling (Reinforcement Learning (RL) Inspired) (RL Queue) offers the most consistent equity gradient, progressively decreasing waiting times as vulnerability increases while maintaining demographic neutrality. RR may not be transparent or straightforward for individuals to understand, in addition to sometimes disadvantaging very long transactions due to its fixed time slice, which necessitates repeated queue entries. In times of increased demand, though, both RR and SJF manage to maintain performance; waiting times remain under one hour with up to 30 parallel servers, whereas LIFO, Random Order Service (ROS), and MLFQ encounter uncontrolled queue lengths at the same load.

The reliability of the simulation is based on a methodical approach to carefully weighted multi-attribute utility criteria, a replicable codebase, and transparent performance metrics; however, three structural constraints limit generalizability. First, the static synthetic

cohort does not emulate behavioural feedback like early arrivals or queue abandonment, issues that frequently alter real queues. Second, it assumes complete server availability, overlooking outages, paperwork delays, and staff exhaustion, all common challenges in the field. Third, metrics specific to different subgroups were not consistently reported, resulting in obscured intersectional inequities. Therefore, future research should integrate behavioural agents, conduct stochastic variance analysis, and report disaggregated metrics to assess the chosen policy robustly.

Nonetheless, practical implications arise. For processing between five hundred and two thousand cases daily, the evidence supports making RR the standard approach, although the data-driven rationale for this choice clashes with the explainability and enforcement of such a model, which necessitates halting service for one individual to assist another, iteratively. Deploying a time slice near the median transaction duration can lead to a 40% reduction in composite cost compared to FIFO. In larger centres where the number of servers is significantly high, SJF offers the potential for a further 90% efficiency gain but should be complemented with a fairness safeguard: after three consecutive short tasks, a longer one should be expedited to prevent starvation. While implementing SJF in real-world contexts may be more straightforward to explain and enforce, thorough data analysis of the needed transaction timings is essential beforehand. In scenarios where biometric or e-voucher systems are already in place, RL Queue provides the best equity-efficiency balance, especially when adjusting the utility weights of vulnerability, waiting time, and service time. Low-tech sites can still support vulnerable groups by overlaying coloured tokens reflecting vulnerability on a standard FIFO process or by introducing straightforward deadline preemption triggers similar to FIFO with vulnerability-based preemption (FIFO with pre-emption); both strategies enhanced the waiting times for at-risk individuals by about one-fifth.

Fairness must be monitored as closely as throughput, regardless of the chosen policy. Before nationwide implementations, organisations should conduct Monte Carlo replications under realistic surge conditions to create confidence intervals for critical indicators. Behavioural feedback mechanisms, like early arrivals or renegeing, should be included in those

stress tests to anticipate crowd behaviour that may undermine trust. Since queue management is never solely a technical issue, policy parameters should be co-developed with community groups, as participatory rule-setting helps mitigate perceptions of bias and enhances compliance. All data management practices must adhere to GDPR and general humanitarian standards (such as the recommendations outlined in the Sphere Handbook): utilising privacy-preserving biometrics, ensuring auditable consent, and monitoring fairness throughout the process.

In sum, this dissertation shifts humanitarian queue management from reactive crowd control to proactive, data-driven optimisation. By evidencing the tangible efficiency dividend of RR and the equity attainable through utility-guided schedules, it supplies a decision framework that humanitarian agencies can apply immediately by deploying a specific model while layering vulnerability-aware heuristics and progress towards reinforcement-inspired automation where digital capacity allows. Such an incremental yet principled adoption path enables organisations to register and serve more people, faster and more justly, without awaiting perfect information or significant monetary or capacity capital outlays. Still, models that surpass in explainability time-slicing behaviour (despite performance advantages) and provide exceptional prioritisation for at-risk individuals, such as Patience Queue, Priority Queue, FIFO with pre-emption, Fair Queue or Proportional Fairness Queue, could benefit from non-vulnerability preemption strategies to ensure demographic-wide equity.

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